

Machine Learning based Analysis and Design of Pediatric Epileptic Seizure Detection using Electroencephalogram Signals

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by

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I, Satarupa Chakrabarti hereby declare that the work which is being presented in the thesis entitled “Machine Learning based Analysis and Design of Pediatric Epileptic Seizure Detection using Electroencephalogram Signals”, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Computer Science and Engineering and submitted by me to KIIT, Deemed to be University, Bhubaneswar is an authentic record of my own work. The matter embodied in this thesis has not been submitted by me for the award of any other degree of this or any other University/Institute

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ABSTRACT

Epilepsy is a nervous system chaos that describes the distinctive nature of seizures. A seizure is a sudden, transient aberration in the brain's electrical activity that produces disruptive symptoms. These symptoms range between a lapse in attention, a sensory hallucination, or a whole-body convulsion. In the current scenario of disease and disorders in the world population, epilepsy stands out to be the third commonest neurological disorder that is affecting millions of people across the continents. The most common non-invasive tool that is preferred for studying brain activity of epileptic patient is the electroencephalogram (EEG).

Electroencephalogram (EEG) signal is a way to assess the current flow that takes place during synaptic excitation of the dendrites present in the cerebral cortex. Conventional approaches for examining an EEG signal for epileptic seizure detection are time-overwhelming. Over the years and with time, in every aspect of human life the amount of data and information is ever increasing. In the last two decades machine learning has become the main backbone of the information technology. In different application domain machine learning is considered to be a key part in the cutting-edge system. The main aim of machine learning research is to build algorithms that would have a general purpose and would come with practical values. In the world of medical science machine learning have made its mark by designing different expert systems with the help of algorithms and methods. Neuroscience is one area which can be immensely benefitted from the inclusion of machine learning. Apart from various neurological disorders, epilepsy is one of the most sought-after areas where for the last few decades work is progressing. Machine learning plays its role in developing and designing methods that would help in detection, monitoring and prediction of an epileptic seizure attack. Machine learning is slowly but gradually making its mark in the world of biomedical science and bridging the gap between both worlds by designing methods and framework suitable for real time applications.

Developing newer ways to deal with this unpredictable nature of epilepsy attack, early detection of seizures and generation of instant warning systems might help people in improving their quality of life. The detection and prediction system will also help in the diagnostic evaluation of the patients that would not only help in epilepsy surgery

but also in understanding the latent characteristics of epilepsy and dynamics of the brain during such attacks. Therefore, the aim of the work is to address the challenges faced during design of automated seizure detection system. The ultimate goal is to develop a framework that would be efficient in seizure detection and monitoring. To achieve the desired feat, different feature extraction techniques (mean, standard deviation, DWT, DFT, energy) have been applied for extracting suitable features using a moving window technique. The extracted features are then used in traditional machine learning techniques. Comparative study has also been undertaken to assess the efficacy of the applied approaches. This helped in determining the appropriate approach that would be effective in designing a real-time cost-effective method. Also, the work aims at designing a method that is patient independent as well as channel independent. This would help in developing a system that is robust and adaptable. To validate this aspect, the present work has been corroborated and tested in a non-invasive and an invasive dataset. This helped in understanding the seizure discerning capacity of the proposed approach when faced with an unknown and unseen dataset that contained EEG signals recorded in a different method. Apart from traditional classifiers, two deep learning approaches have also been applied for discerning seizure signals from raw electroencephalogram recordings. Therefore, the work undertakes a comprehensive designing approach to develop an epileptic seizure detector framework that displays the possibility of real-time monitoring of epileptic patients while providing better solution that could lead towards enhancement in the quality of living of patients suffering from epilepsy.

Keywords: Epilepsy; Electroencephalogram; Seizure Detection; Feature Extraction; Traditional Machine Learning; Deep Learning Approach

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List of Abbreviations in Alphabetic Order

ADC	Analog-to-digital converter
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
AUC	Area Under the Curve
Bi-LSTM	Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory
BR-SNN	Bayesian Regularized Shallow Neural Network
C	Central
CHB-MIT	Children's Hospital Boston Massachusetts Institute of Technology
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CV	Cross Validation
CWT	Continuous Wavelet Transform
DB	Daubechies Wavelet
DCNN	Deep Convolutional Neural Network
DFT	Discrete Fourier Transform
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DT	Decision Tree
DWT	Discrete Wavelet Transform
EBC	Effective Brain Connectivity
EEG	Electroencephalogram
EEMD	Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition
ENS	Ensemble Learning
ETTL-TSK-FS	Enhanced Transductive Transfer Learning Takagi-Sugeno-Kang Fuzzy System
EWT	Empirical Wavelet Transform
F	Frontal
FBC	Functional Brain Connectivity
FalseNeg	False Negative
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
FalsePos	False Positive
GMM-HMM	Gaussian Mixture Hidden Markov Model
GNMM	Genetic Neural Mathematical Method
GRU	Gated Recurrent Unit

GST	Generalized Stockwell Transform
HVD	Hilbert Vibration Decomposition
ICA	Independent Component Analysis
ICFS	Improved Correlation-Based Feature Selection
iEEG	Intracranial Encephalogram
IoT	Internet of Things
JME	Juvenile Myoclonic Epilepsy
kNN	k-Nearest Neighbors
LDA	Linear Discriminant Analysis
LND	Log-Normal Distribution
LOO	Leave-One-Out
LSDA	Locality Sensitive Discriminant Analysis
LS-SVM	Least Square Support Vector Machine
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory Network
LUT	Look Up Table
MAV	Mean Absolute Value
MCC	Matthew's Correlation Coefficient
MENN	Modular Effective Neural Networks
MFNN	Modular Frequency Neural Networks
MIC	Maximal Information Coefficient
MLMN	Multi-Level Modular Network
MLPNN	Multilayer Perceptron Neural Network
MODWT	Maximal Overlap Discrete Wavelet Transform
MRW-FFWNN	Multidimensional Radial Wavelons Feed-Forward Wavelet Neural Network
O	Occipital
P	Parietal
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
rag-ROA	rag-Rider Optimization Algorithm
RBFN	Radial Basis Function Network
ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit
RF	Random Forest
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network

ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve
RP	Recurrence Plot
RQA	Recurrence Quantification Analysis
SCANN	Stacking Correspondence Analysis and Nearest Neighbor
SDCN	Semi-Dilated Convolutional Network
SGCN	Sequential Graph Convolutional Network
SMOTE	Synthetic Minority Over-Sampling Technique
SOC	System-On-Chip
STD	Standard Deviation
STFT	Short Time Fourier Transform
SWEC	Sleep-Wake-Epilepsy-Center
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition
SVM	Support Vector Machine
T	Temporal
TrueNeg	True Negative
TruePos	True Positive
TQWT	Tunable-Q Wavelet Transform
VAR	Variance
VHDL	Very High-Speed Integrated Circuit Hardware Description Language
VLSI	Very-Large-Scale Integration
VMD	Variational Mode Decomposition

Chapter 1: Introduction

“The worst part of having seizures is knowing that they can happen anytime and even though drugs control mine most of the time they occasionally breakthrough.”

Epileptic seizures are brief periods of complicated hyper synchronization and hyper activity of a large number of neurons inside the brain. One of the authors described seizure to be similar to a storm or like an earthquake only with the difference that this electrical storm takes place inside the brain [1]. The frequently asked question related to epilepsy is “what do we mean by a seizure?” and “when and how can we detect the seizure?” but the answer to them is elusive as there is no constant technique or way in which seizure can be detected with complete accuracy.

1.1 Epilepsy

Epilepsy is an irregularity in the central nervous system that is inborn in nature and manifests through recurrent seizures [2]. A seizure occurs suddenly due to the abnormal firing of neurons that results in out-of-order manifestation that is brief in nature. The extent of symptoms is wide and lies between failing to pay attention, hallucination or convulsion of the whole body [3]. Epilepsy is considered to be a group of different syndromes rather than being considered as a single disease. There can be various factors responsible for epilepsy. It can be an effect of genetic mutation in a molecular process that controls neuronal behavior, composition or migration. It can also emerge as a result of trauma to the brain like stroke or head injury, brain malignancy or cerebral infection [4]. Around the world, nearly 1% of the world population or fifty million suffer from epilepsy [5]. According to statistics, nearly 3 million people suffer due to epilepsy and it is the third most occurring neurological disorder just behind Alzheimer’s disease and stroke. The prevalence of epilepsy is assessed to be around 44 persons out of 100,000 per year [6]. Almost one person out of every 100 has the chance of experiencing a seizure attack in their lifetime [7]. Out of the three million patients, nearly 1.2 million individuals have a random erratic seizure that lingers in spite of treatment using more than one anti-epileptic drug. These kinds of seizures are generally known as incurable seizures.

Generally, a seizure that is incurable medically greatly confines the freedom as well as the movement of a person and thus leads to social awkwardness and economic difficulty. Refractory seizures involve consequences such as burns, fractures in the skull, lacerations or even death [8]. The effect of seizures uncontrolled in nature imparts

negative effect on the family members as well as friends and the community. Therefore, there is an urgent need for alternative treatment and therapy that would prove to be helpful for not only the patient but their family to deal with seizures and their consequents [9]. Even when epilepsy gets under control because of the drugs, patients suffer from anxiety attacks due to its erratic nature. Thus, the possibility of accurate detection of seizures and ahead of time prediction will help to check seizures and limit accidents and injuries [10].

1.2 Pediatric Epilepsy

Seizures are the most frequent juvenile neurologic condition, affecting 4 percent to 10% of children in their first 16 years of life [11]. Children under the age of three have the highest occurrence, with older children having a lower frequency. According to epidemiologic research, around 150,000 children have an unprovoked seizure for the first time each year [12]. Fever, meningitis, metabolic imbalance, exposure to a toxin, brain injury, tumor, or other diseases are all possible causes of pediatric seizures. Sometimes cause remains unanswered [13]. Pediatric seizures, like adult seizures, are split into two categories: generalized seizures, which affect the entire brain, i.e., the seizure manifestation is felt throughout the brain, and partial seizures, which, unlike generalized seizures, affect only a single region of the brain. At times partial seizure changes to generalized seizure – such type is known as partial seizure with secondary generalization. Partial or focal seizure has two main types – simple partial or complex partial. Table 1.1 shows the various types of seizures. GTC (Generalized tonic-clonic seizure) is considered to be the most common generalized seizure. The seizure begins with stiffening of the limbs (the tonic phase), which is followed by jerky movement of the limbs and face (the clonic phase) [14]. During the tonic phase, there is a decrease or cessation of breathing altogether, thus resulting in cyanosis (blueing) of the lips, nail beds, and sometimes the face. With the setting in of the clonic (jerking) phase, the breathing resumes but still stays irregular. Generalized absence seizure also known as petit mal seizures results in momentary loss of awareness that lasts for only a few seconds [14]. This type of seizure comes without any warning and is known to have no after-effect and its prevalence is more in children. Generalized atypical absence seizure generally occurs at a frequency that is in the range of less than 2.5 Hz. Loss of awareness occurs only when this type of seizure is present in the bi-frontal or bi-fronto central part of the brain [14]. In generalized myoclonic seizure, a single or short burst of generalized spike and wave or poly-spike and wave brain activity is detected.

Myoclonic seizures are rapid, brief contractions in body movements, that is mostly present in both side of the body [12]. EEG recordings of generalized tonic seizures vary because muscle artefacts can sometimes overpower them. The brain activity is in the range of 10 Hz which is mostly of short duration and shows postictal slow activity. When generalized atonic seizures occur in people with Lennox-Gastaut syndrome, the EEG recordings are quite similar to those of generalized tonic seizures. Atonic seizures manifest as a sudden loss of muscle tone. Table 1.2 presents different syndromes that are related to pediatric epilepsy [12].

Table 1.1 Broad categories of seizure and their types

Category	Types	Location	Manifestation
Partial	Simple	One area on one side of the brain	Depending on location body parts affected.
	Complex	In any lobe of the brain	Alteration in the awareness.
Generalized	Tonic-Clonic	Starts from one hemisphere and spreads (focal to bilateral)	Stiffening of muscles, loss of consciousness, jerky movements of limbs.
	Absence	Both side of brain at the same time.	Momentary loss in the awareness.
	Atypical Absence	Anterior part of brain	Staring, eye blinking, slight jerky movement may occur.
	Myoclonic	Frontal lobe of the brain	Rapid jerking or twitching of muscle.
	Tonic	Anterior part of the brain	Tone increases, body becomes stiff.
	Atonic	In any one part of the brain	Sudden drop or loss of tone of the muscle.

Table 1.2 Pediatric epileptic syndromes

Types	Age	Presentation
Infantile Spasm	Infants aged 3 – 9 months	Eye drop or head drop.

Typical Myoclonic Spasm	(Earlier or later presentation do occur)	
Febrile Seizure	6 months – 5years	Focal manifestation, less than 15 seconds.
Benign Rolandic Epilepsy Generalized Tonic-Clonic	3 – 13 years	Speech arrest, guttural sounds or facial numbness.
Lennox- Gastaut Syndrome (Occipital Epilepsy)	3 – 5 years	Visual symptoms.
Absence Seizure (Petit Mal Epilepsy)	Begins 3 – 11 years Between 5 – 8 years (Most often)	As frequent as 100 times a day. Brief staring spells, fluttering of eyelids.
Juvenile Myoclonic Epilepsy (JME)	Teen years (5 – 15 years)	Generalized tonic clonic seizures, myoclonic jerks or staring spells.

1.3 Method to Record Electroencephalogram (EEG) Signals

In the human brain during prenatal development, the neural activity starts around the 17th to 23rd week and are representative of different movements of the entire body. This presumption is taken as a motivation for using different advanced signal processing methods to the EEG or electroencephalogram signals for measuring and understanding various brain activity and the underlying working of the brain during disorders such as epilepsy [15]. EEG signal is a way to assess the current flow that takes place during synaptic excitation of the dendrites present in the cerebral cortex. Synaptic current is produced when brain cells get activated. The brain waves vary from patient to patient in respect of frequency and amplitude of signals. Brain waves as seen in Fig.1.1 are usually characterized depending on the frequency range. When arranged in the ascending order of the frequency range the rhythms are alpha (α), theta (θ), beta (β), delta (δ) and gamma (γ). The very first electrical activities of the neurons were recorded using simple galvanometers. In recent years, the EEG recording system contains an array of delicate electrodes, a set of differential amplifiers (one for every channel) followed by filters, and needle (pen)-type registers. Previously, recording from

multichannel EEGs was plotted on plain paper or paper with a grid. Gradually computerized systems came in place that digitized and stored the recordings. Also, an analog-to-digital converter (ADC) is present that converts the signals from analog to digital. The recording of electrical activity is crucial and a lot depends on the types of electrodes [16].

Fig.1.1. Different brain waves with their frequencies. [160]

The conventional electrode positioning system, also known as the 10-20 electrode positioning, has been recommended for the recording of the electrical signals of the brain by the International Federation of Societies for Electroencephalography and Clinical Neurophysiology for 21 electrodes (excluding the earlobe electrodes). The earlobe electrodes are generally called A1 and A2 and are connected respectively to both earlobes as reference electrodes [17]. The placement of electrodes in the 10-20 system is based on some specific measurements depending on anatomic landmarks based on which the electrode intervals are calculated (10% or 20%) and placed on the skull. On the left side of the hemisphere, the electrodes are odd-numbered while in the right hemisphere of the brain they are even-numbered. When large numbers of electrodes are used for the recordings, the electrodes are placed equidistant from each other. The different lobes in the brain are denoted using different letters along with the number to identify the hemisphere. The letters that are used for the Frontal, Temporal,

Central, Parietal and Occipital lobes are, F, T, C, P and O respectively. “z” is used with either of these letters to present the midline electrode. Electrodes can be placed in different ways and this is known as a montage. The EEG signals can be recorded with the following electrode placements [15, 17].

Bipolar Montage: In this setting one pair of electrodes make up the individual channels. Each channel records the difference between two adjacent electrodes as seen in Fig. 1.3. The whole placement consists of a series of electrodes combinations.

Referential Montage: In this type of montage setting the difference between an electrode and a particular pre-determined reference electrode is recorded. There is no specification for the position of the reference electrode and can be placed anywhere other than the recording electrodes. Generally, the preferable position is the midline as they represent neither of the two hemispheres. Sometimes the earlobes or the mastoid is considered as the reference point.

Average Reference Montage: In this technique, the summation of the output recorded at each amplifier is taken and the average is calculated. The average is considered as the common reference for every channel. The placement is shown in Fig. 1.2 (b).

Laplacian Montage: In this montage placement as seen in Fig. 1.2 (c), the channels present the difference between the electrode and a weighted average of the surrounding electrodes.

Fig.1.2. (a) Longitudinal montage (b) Average reference montage (c) Laplacian montage. [161]

Fig.1.3. Bipolar montage. [161]

1.4 Machine Learning Approaches to Detect Epilepsy

The last few decades have seen an ever-growing number of scientific fields benefitting from the advancement in machine learning approaches and in recent years that trend has reached the medical domain. The recent development in the area related to neurology and brain interfaces have shown commendable progress that has been able to address various challenges related to the domain. Epilepsy being one such neurological condition comes with its own inherent problems and challenges. As the disease expression changes over time and vary across patients, thus generalized

diagnosis and treatment across patients in a uniform manner becomes difficult. Also, the amount of data generated during an EEG recording is huge thus making it difficult to enforce continuous monitoring. Manual reviewing of the EEG signal is time intensive. To tackle such issues, machine learning approaches presents a plethora of options that can be explored to develop automated seizure detection and monitoring systems that would reduce the burden of manually reviewing individual recordings or monitoring sessions. The idea of designing an automated model that will have the capability of identifying seizure segments from non-seizure segments with the aid of machine learning approaches have greatly influenced the present work.

Seizure detection commonly refers to the application of an algorithm that would automatically identify a seizure that is about to occur by interpreting different biologic signals that are recorded from epileptic patients. The pivotal objective is to acquire the signals and study them [18]. The analysis is done through the transformation of the signals to obtain the desired output that would suggest if a patient is currently in a state of seizure or not. The most crucial step is adjustment and modification of the signal that helps in accurately assessing the recordings of individual patients. When it comes to seizure detection, the machine learning algorithm can only detect the seizure after it has started and the presence is recorded [19]. While in seizure prediction the algorithm foretells the presence of an imminent seizure before the seizure can occur. The thin line of separation between detection and prediction algorithms gets a little bit disarrayed on the ambiguity that follows as to what should be taken as the starting point for the prediction that could be based on the presence of a specific pattern or signal. Machine learning-based seizure detection framework is efficient in not only detecting an ongoing seizure but also contributes to providing detailed analysis of the seizure that would eventually help in dealing with epilepsy [20]. Seizure detection algorithm in support with closed-loop systems may provide a fast solution to seizures that are fairly early in their onset thus diminishing the complexity and thus checking the rate in which they advance. Different types of algorithms are present for this detection purpose and contain two major steps. Firstly, befitting features and characteristics are enumerated from the raw data like features of the EEG recordings, various movements associated with the recordings and other biomarkers that are present. Secondly, a base criterion is decided upon depending on which the presence or absence of seizure is determined. The second phase has a particular name attributed to it as classification which either requires a base value also known as the threshold value or a base model from which

various derivations are made. The notable features are selected in such a way that it compromises neither the accuracy nor the speed of detection. When the attributes and conditions are designed for the model, they can be applied to the whole dataset or a subset like for an individual patient [21]. At the moment practical application of seizure detection algorithms and methods have provided satisfactory results with promising accuracy. But seizure prediction continues to be a wide-open problem that does not have a steady approach that would predict seizures correctly and with minimum delay. Practical approach for seizure detection algorithm is to either design a model that would identify seizure depending on certain particular signals that seizures generally have in common, known as signal patterns. The other way is to construct an all-round seizure detection algorithm that will detect different kinds of abnormal activities in brain signals thus implementing a whole range of data about the dynamics of the brain related to seizure patients. Both the approaches have limitations of their own. While in the first method since only particular patterns are taken into consideration so rest of the features may be left undetected. In the second approach as the whole dynamic of the brain is considered so chances of presence of artifacts and other events may be present. The major hurdle in the designing of seizure detection algorithm is detection of the earliest change in signal that may have the highest possibility of ending as clinical seizure. The characteristics of scalp EEG recording that have the ability to perplex the seizure detection task is the inconsistent manifestation of seizure across patients. The rhythmic activity as well as the spectral features of seizure depending on the location and various channels vary across every individual patient. EEG signature also varies from patient to patient and sometimes abnormal activity of one patient may look similar to non-seizure activity of another patient. Also, deep-seated neural activities are seldom reflected in scalp EEG recordings and may be presented as eye flutters or contraction in muscular movements. Such seizures pose as hindrance in the effective working of the seizure detection algorithm.

1.5 Recent Hardware Developments Related to Epilepsy

In recent years, significant attention is directed towards biomedical research on designing energy-efficient, and both invasive and non-invasive real-time integrated seizure detection circuits. Seizure detection systems that are automated and transportable are suitable for patients with epilepsy and to integrate effective training and accurate seizure detection ability, systems are getting implemented on chips. Authors have used both hardware as well as IoT-based approaches to develop efficient

detection units. An implantable hyper-synchronous signal detection circuit [22] has been designed that has the capability of constantly monitoring the neuronal activity so that the pulse generated during seizure onset can be identified. To reduce the power consumption of the model, a hardware-in-loop approach has been used that has minimal hardware but provided facility for either non-invasive (wearable) approach or invasive (implantable) approach or even a combination of both. Along with the detector, one of the approaches has a combination of an open-loop and closed-loop system of drug delivery mechanism that released necessary medication when signals crossed a particular threshold. To reduce the cost of wearable and portable devices for the automatic detection of epileptic seizures, wireless body sensors have been deployed in the health sector. Even though the body sensors are an alternate solution but the key difficulty lies in developing energy-efficient sensors. Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) has also been used by authors for designing hardware-based automated epilepsy seizure detection systems. Cloud-related biomedical implants and sensors have enhanced the mobile healthcare sector, making it an emerging field of innovative research and also helping in designing effective seizure detection units.

The reason behind inclusion of hardware development related to epilepsy seizure detection is to present a brief idea about the recent development related to this area and also how the present work can be directed towards it in future for a possible hardware implementation.

1.6 Motivation

Worldwide estimation projects 12% of the population to be suffering from epilepsy that ranges from infants to adults. The occurrence of seizure cannot be foretold and this is the main cause that makes humans powerless in front of it because a certain range of uncertainty is related to seizure attacks which have a direct impact on the daily life of not only the patient but also the caregivers. Generally during the onset and after the occurrence of seizure are the two periods that halt the day-to-day activity of patients, other than that presence of epilepsy remains hidden. Developing newer ways to deal with this unpredictable nature of epilepsy attack, early detection of seizures and generation of instant warning systems might help people in improving their quality of life. The detection and prediction system will also help in the diagnostic evaluation of the patients that would not only help in epilepsy surgery but also in understanding the latent characteristics of epilepsy and dynamics of the brain during such attacks. Automated seizure detection systems come with the potential of providing therapeutic

therapies like drug infusion, electrical stimulation and bio feedbacks which can be given as an answer to detection of seizure. The challenges and the developments have acted as an impetus towards designing efficient seizure detection systems that would help in accurately detecting seizures.

The present work is focused on efficient detection of epileptic seizures from EEG signals. Keeping in mind the current scenario, a treatment gap exists in the medical domain where fast detection of disease and its treatment is still an issue at large. To bridge this gap, the work is an attempt to close this gap to a small extent. With the help of the present work, if the trained model can be deployed via cloud-based platforms, then EEG signals can be used directly from patient to detect presence of seizure. Also, continuous monitoring of pediatric patients can be ensured where the EEG recordings are analyzed by the trained model to detect any change in the EEG signals that can be detected as an epileptic episode. The proposed work with necessary modifications can be deployed and tested in clinical scenarios which would be beneficial for patients and would have a positive impact on the society.

1.7 Objectives of the Work

Detection of seizures faces various challenges. Therefore, the objective is to overcome the hurdles and develop a framework that would be efficient in seizure detection and monitoring.

- Contribute to developing a system that is patient and channel independent and has the possibility to be implemented in real-time scenarios. A time-domain implementation of seizure detection that emphasizes on pediatric patients. Different wavelet families have been used for extraction of appropriate features from non-invasive EEG signals to find a suitable pattern. The extracted features act as input in a traditional artificial neural network classifier to detect between non-seizure and seizure signals. A simple hardware approach has been suggested for convenient recognition and monitoring of pediatric epilepsy, utilizing MATLAB/SIMULINK and Arduino.
- Comparing different machine learning algorithms to deduce an approach that would work effectively in any type of EEG recording. To compare between features and classifiers, five diverse features and four different classifiers have been used for distinguishing epileptic seizures. To extract suitable feature patterns a moving window of 1 second has been introduced so that subtle changes occurring in the EEG signals can be effectively captured for further processing. These features are

used in the different classifiers to compare the efficacy of seizure detection. Also, instead of using cross-validation, the test sample technique has been considered for validating the classifier models.

- Developing a useful method with the help of a deep learning algorithm that would decrease the false detections and increase the accuracy of detection. Instead of using processed EEG signals, a long short-term memory (LSTM) based deep learning algorithm has been designed for efficient seizure detection from raw EEG recordings. The LSTM model has contributed in analyzing the integral temporal characteristics of EEG recordings and as handcrafted features are not used hence helped in substantially reducing the time required for preprocessing of the signals. From the perspective of deep learning approach, the model used is devoid of complicated network thus raising the chance of a real-time implementation.

1.8 Organization of the Thesis

The thesis is organized in different chapters as mentioned below:

In **Chapter 2** background research is provided on the works of different authors related to epilepsy seizure detection. The literature survey consists of studies and experiments that have been done using different machine learning techniques. The chapter has been further subdivided according to specific subsections related to different seizure detection approaches. The literature survey gives not only a brief idea about the works that have been done to date but also helps us to understand the current scenario and the limitations that come along with the various methods.

Chapter 3 contains the first proposed approach where a time-domain implementation has been proposed for epileptic seizure detection using discrete wavelet transformation and an artificial neural network. The subsections highlight the technique used along with the architecture of the proposed method and detailed discussion on results achieved.

In **Chapter 4** test sample method has been suggested for epileptic seizure detection using five different features and four different classifiers. A comparison analysis has been performed based on detection capacity of seizure instances of each classifier. A moving window of 1 second has been used to extract suitable feature patterns.

Chapter 5 highlights a long short-term memory-based novel deep learning method for efficient seizure detection from raw EEG signals. The subsections of the chapter describe the architectural structure of the proposed method along with the training and testing scenario.

Chapter 6 accounts for the main findings of the work along with the efficiency analysis of seizure detection with other methods. It also highlights the various limitations that are faced while developing a seizure detection model

Lastly, **Chapter 7** presents the conclusion of the three proposed approaches and also highlights the future direction of epilepsy seizure detection.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

As epilepsy is one of the most common diseases currently affecting the human population, researchers have spent the last four decades working to better understand epilepsy and the inherent features of neuronal activity that accompany an epilepsy attack, as well as to detect and predict the onset of a seizure. Gotman, who created patient non-specific detectors in 1982, is accredited with the initial work. Over the years works have been conducted in great length. The main reason behind the growing interest of researchers is the development of newer techniques in addressing medical problems. The pillars that form the base of the work are analysis of electroencephalograms (EEG) signals and designing different techniques that will help in providing an alternate way of treatment for patients suffering from epilepsy. The subsequent subsections extensively highlight the works of various researchers specifically in the area of epileptic seizure detection.

2.1 Statistical-based Methods

When classifiers are applied directly to raw EEG signals, there lies a chance where the classifier might fail to identify the underlying patterns. Thus, choosing relevant features from EEG recordings is an important aspect of seizure detection. Usually, different statistical features are extracted using various transformation approaches, such as discrete wavelet transform [23, 24, 25, 26, 27], maximal overlap discrete wavelet transform [28], continuous wavelet transformation, short-time Fourier transform [29], discrete Fourier transformation [30], singular value decomposition, intrinsic mode functions [31], discrete cosine transformation, empirical mode decomposition [32], symplectic geometry decomposition [33], principal dynamic modes [34], Stein kernel-based sparse representation [35], and many more. Bhattacharya and Pachori [36] in their work used EWT (empirical wavelet transform) to extract joint instantaneous amplitudes and frequencies from multivariate EEG signals. To drastically reduce the frequency of erroneous alarms while detecting the presence of seizures and improve the detection rate, Ibrahim et al. [37] in their proposed work used Slantlet Transform and sparse coding. Cross frequency coupling has been used by [38] to generate an alarm before a seizure attack. Their approach provided an approximate time frame along with prior warnings to a patient suffering from epilepsy. Fei et al. [39] developed a novel method in the domain of fractional Fourier transform and Lyapunov exponent was applied for determining the fractional-order obtained from the signal.

As brain rhythms are made up of different bands, to analyze the energy distribution in each band, Tsiouris et al. [40] in their work used short-time Fourier transformation. They used EEG segments and tried identifying the energy distribution in each of the brain rhythms. Wavelet transformation has been one of the most readily used feature extraction techniques and different variations of wavelet transform have been applied by authors over the years. Harmonic wavelet packet transformation has been used in [41] to extract better harmonic multiresolution from EEG signals. In the time domain, a tunable-Q wavelet has been used by Patidar et al. [42] for representing the sparsity and non-stationary characteristics of EEG signals. Tunable-Q wavelet helps in decomposing a signal into specific band limited sub-bands for better feature extraction. Other than wavelet transformation, the correlation between phases of consecutive epochs in an EEG signal has been by Parvez et al. [43] for extracting the global features related to it. Ahmad et al. [44] applied group invariant scattering for extracting relevant features before using it in a classifier for pediatric seizure detection. Zhu et al. [45] studied the spatial-temporal complexities of EEG signals using entropy-based methods – permutation entropy and sample entropy. Authors have used statistical [46] as well as spectral approaches for extracting significant features from EEG recordings.

In [47], authors used a wide range of feature extraction techniques such as Min Amplitude, Zero Crossing Rate, Skewness, Max Amplitude, Mode, Energy, Kurtosis, Mean, Standard Deviation, Median, Entropy, Variance, Signal to Noise Ratio, Coefficient of Variation, and Mean Power, to study the inherent features of EEG signals. To analyze the signal based on frequency, Yavuz et al. [48] used mel frequency cepstral coefficients to compute the features that depended on the bandwidths of the filter bank. Authors used spectral density maps [49, 50] to present the power distribution in EEG signals and the certain changes that occur in the power spectral density during an epileptic attack. Instead of using multiple features, Thilagaraj et al. [51] used a single feature in the form of Tsallis entropy that decreased the computational time of their proposed method. Spectral entropy has also been used by Hadiyoso et al. [52] for understanding the dynamics of EEG signals. A feature learning method loosely based on L1-penalized robust regression has been used in [53] to distinguish the most relevant features that are seen during a seizure onset. Zhang et al. [54] used different approaches of feature extraction along with a new method of fuzzy distribution entropy to analyze EEG signals. Kruskal-Wallis test was performed by the authors to select the most significant features.

Guo et al. [55] used a lightweight technique in the form of extended correlation-based feature selection for analyzing and eliminating unnecessary features that did not pertain to improving seizure classification. For characterization of the brain rhythm sequences during an epileptic seizure onset, the reassigned smoothed pseudo-Wigner-Ville distribution has been used by Wen Li et al. [56]. An advanced method that hybridizes PCA and t-statistics has been used by Rahman et al. [57] for extraction as well as reduction of feature dimension. In [58], authors showed that cross-bispectrum could be employed in retrieving important features from multichannel EEG signals. A lesser-known temporal-based method of multivariate statistical process control has been used by Ruksar et al. [59] for analyzing seizure phases in long-term EEG recordings. The clustering of useful data with the help of functional principal component analysis has been applied by Xie et al. [60] for analyzing random EEG signals. A novel approach by Migliorelli et al. [61], known as the S-Transform Gaussian mixture detection algorithm has been used by authors to detect high-frequency oscillations present in EEG signals through several time-frequency features.

2.2 Black Box and Non-Black Box Classifiers

Authors have used different types of classifiers for developing effective seizure detection systems. Ibrahim and Maizoub [62] implemented one of the traditional classifiers in the form of k-nearest neighbors (kNN) for the automatic classification of EEG signals. The authors emphasized the simplicity and adaptive learning capability of the classifier that made it suitable for hardware implementation. Similar to [62], Siddiqui et al. [63] have used different black box and non-black box classifiers for analyzing and comparing the classification efficacy of different classifiers. Identifying patterns emerging over time from EEG signals marred with noise is a long-standing issue faced by researchers in the field of neuroscience. Ke et al. [64] used a shallow-dense network for better adaptation to evolving patterns in multivariate EEG signals with the help of maximal information coefficient (MIC). The coefficients extracted helped in the sequential synchronization of channels that portrayed the developing patterns. Lahmiri [65] used the support vector machine (SVM) with different kernels and based on generalized Hurst exponent for analyzing abnormal EEG signals. The author also showed that multifractal-based features have significant variation between normal and interictal phases when analyzed using statistical tests. Satapathy et al. [66] used multiple kernels such as Multi-quadric, Gaussian, and Inverse-multi-quadric for the radial basis function network (RBFN) to understand the effectiveness of their

proposed approach while applying various combinations of seizure-free segments, seizure segments and healthy segments.

For differentiating epileptiform patterns during interictal and ictal phases, multilayer perceptron has been used in [67]. Energy from the EEG signals, along with norm and log energy entropy has been used for extracting the relevant features vectors before being fed into the perceptron for classification. Multu [68] exploited transforming EEG recordings using Hilbert vibration decomposition (HVD) for differentiating epileptic signals with the least square support vector machine (LS-SVM) as the classifier. LS-SVM has proven to be effective in signal processing due to its abridged computational complexity. Sharmila and Geethanjali [69] have used time-domain features such as length of the waveform, changes in slope sign and zero-crossings for studying the changes in EEG signals during a seizure attack. Traditional classifiers like naïve Bayes and support vector machines have been used for recognizing the pattern generated during the onset of an epileptic attack. Apart from the support vector machine, a feedforward neural network has been used for designing the classification system. Authors in [70] applied wavelet-based feature extraction and addressed their proposed method for seizure detection as MRW-FFWNN (multidimensional radial wavelons feed-forward wavelet neural network). Three-fold cross-validation selected the final class decision along with different weighted voting strategies for the final classification of EEG signals.

Before features are used in the classifiers, they are reduced using linear discriminant analysis (LDA) [71] and locality sensitive discriminant analysis (LSDA) [72] to decrease the number of attributes. Embedded system has been used using EEMD (ensemble empirical mode decomposition) and TQWT (tunable-Q wavelet transform) algorithms with least squares support vector machine (LSSVM), multilayer perceptron neural networks (MLPNN), and random forest (RF) for implementing real-time seizure detection module [73]. While Bayesian regularized shallow neural network (BR-SNNs) has been used by Yadav et al. [74] for studying epileptic seizures. Prominent patterns in the signal have been identified using variational mode decomposition (VMD) and data augmentation has been done by the authors to handle the class imbalance problem. The random forest (RF) classifier has been used to address the problem of class imbalance and Mursalin et al. [75] used an improved correlation-based feature selection method (ICFS) along with RF for detecting epileptic seizures. Different feature extraction techniques such as maximal overlap discrete wavelet transform (MODWT),

log-normal distribution (LND) [76], generalized Stockwell transform (GST) and singular value decomposition (SVD) [77] have been used for identifying changes in EEG signal before being fed to the ensemble classifier of random forest for seizure identification.

2.3 Deep Learning Methods

In recent years deep learning approaches have authoritatively confirmed their superiority over traditional machine learning methods in most areas of research. Neuroscience is also not devoid of the benefits of deep learning methods that showcase competent learning capabilities due to its wide and complex frameworks. Hence, there has been a noticeable shift in the selection of classifiers, from relying on traditional algorithms to focusing on deep learning methods. Convolutional neural networks (CNN) [78, 79], recurrent neural networks (RNN), and long short-term memory networks (LSTM) are the most commonly used deep learning frameworks used for epileptic seizure detection. Talathi [80] explored the efficacy of RNN for seizure detection by using a gated recurrent unit (GRU) that provided satisfactory results in identifying seizures within a window of 5 seconds from the onset of a seizure. As visual inspection for abnormalities in EEG recordings can be time-consuming, so authors in [81] developed a computer-aided seizure diagnosis system with the help of a 13-layer deep convolutional neural network for the automatic distinction of EEG signals. When EEG signals are classified based on multiple classes, traditional methods are seen to falter and hence Ullah et al. [82] proposed a one-dimensional pyramidal CNN that worked on a refinement approach for classifying EEG signals with more than one class. As a refinement approach was used by the authors, this resulted in 60% fewer parameters than traditional CNN frameworks thus decreasing the computational time. To extract relevant features and reduce their dimensions, a deep convolutional autoencoder has been used by Abdelhameed et al. [83]. In a separate work by authors [84], a one-dimensional convolutional neural network has been used for front-end pre-processing of EEG signals before using the features in a bidirectional long short-term memory (Bi-LSTM) recurrent neural network that served at the back-end of their proposed method.

Khan et al. [85] modified wavelet transformation, for studying specific signatures generated by different periods of an EEG signal, by using an array of convolutional filters. The authors have been able to designate a time window where a transition would take place from the preictal to ictal phase and the likely chance of a seizure occurrence.

In some works, authors have tried to lessen the false prediction rate and bring down the rate of false alarms per hour. One such work is [86], where a two-layered long short-term memory (LSTM) network has been used for seizure prediction. Zhou et al. [87] in their work used raw EEG signals on convolutional neural network for exploring the capability of the network in both binary as well as a three-class classification problem. To divulge the correlation existing between consecutive segments of EEG recordings, an LSTM network has been used by Hussein et al. [88]. In separate work, authors [89] used a scalogram or image-like presentation of the EEG signals. To have a better understanding of the generated scalogram, a semi-dilated convolutional network (SDCN) has been designed by the authors that handled the geometry of the scalogram efficiently. The proposed semi-dilated network expanded the receptive field along the image width while preserving the image height. Similar to scalogram, Emami et al. [90] converted EEG signals into plot images with the help of designated time windows. These plot images have been classified by a convolutional neural network and the obtained labels could aid as an index for clinical identification. Image representation of the brain and its signals have also been used by Gomez et al. [91] for accurate identification of epileptic using CNN.

Wen et al. [92] used a combination of deep CNN model and autoencoders to accomplish unsupervised feature extraction from electroencephalogram recordings. According to the authors, autoencoders helped in moving up the convergence time and hence reducing the training time of the classifier. Deep learning algorithms have been used for evaluating seizure detection capability with a reduced number of participating channels. Avcu et al. [93] showed that their developed convolutional network known as SeizNet has been able to identify the presence of seizures efficiently with as few as two channels. Different studies have drawn the comparison between deep learning approaches and traditional methods. In [94], authors have compared different classifiers and it is seen that the LSTM network edged better than other classifiers. Boonyakitanont et al. [95] exploited the concept of 2D-filter decomposition using deep CNN for handling the spatial and temporal domains of the EEG signal. In another work [96], authors designed an ensemble of classifiers that included CNN and termed it ScoreNet for determining the onset and offset of seizure. Their proposed method reduced the false positive rate considerably. CNN has been used for extracting both temporal and spectral features from EEG signals for learning various inherent characteristics of the seizure period and the changes that mark the onset of the seizure

episode [97]. As EEG signals are often marked with the occurrence of ripples, spikes, and ripples-on-spikes during a seizure attack, Medvedev et al. [98] used a long short-term memory neural network for detecting those spikes and ripples. Their method increased the chances of faster diagnostic assessment of patients suffering from intractable epilepsy by helping in identifying the location.

Apart from common LSTM networks, a stacked bidirectional long short-term memory approach has been used in [99] that also incapacitated the vanishing gradient problem faced in the recurrent neural network. The data augmentation method has been used to increase the diversity of EEG samples before being used in a deep convolutional network for further classification [100]. In one of the works, authors [101] used transfer learning and DCNN for extracting features from spectrum density energy diagrams of EEG signals to classify seizures efficiently. Johnrose et al. [102] in their work used a novel optimization technique known as rag-Rider optimization algorithm for training a deep RNN to determine epileptic seizures. In certain supervised approaches, different feature extraction techniques have been used before being fed into the long short-term memory network for the detection of seizures [103]. The relief approach has been used by the authors to lessen the number of extracted features and retain only the active features for further classification. The computational complexity incurred during the processing of EEG signals is diminished using statistical features, as well as local mean decomposition by Hu et al. [104] for preserving the characteristics and extracting relevant features from EEG signals. A bidirectional LSTM has been used by authors that consisted of two LSTM networks with propagation directions opposite to each other. One of the LSTM networks transferred information from front to back while the other relayed it in the opposite direction. Li et al. [105] in their work used convolutional blocks to extract features from EEG signals before giving them as input to a nested LSTM for automatic seizure detection. While Liu et al. [106] compared two deep learning methods namely – a LSTM and a deep CNN for efficient detection of seizures. Out of two, the LSTM model achieved a better seizure detection rate.

2.4 Hybrid Classifiers for Seizure Detection

Numerous approaches have been applied to develop automated and efficient seizure detection units. A combination of one or more methods to design an amalgamated classifier has been used by authors in recent years and such models are usually known as hybrid models or classifiers. Abdulhay et al. [107] used a heterogeneous ensemble learning method for classifying interictal signals from normal signals. They employed

three different classifiers as the base classifier before using a meta-learning algorithm called SCANN for designing the meta classifier and obtaining the outcome from the hybrid classifier. Even the base classifiers have been given different features for categorizing the EEG signals. For a seizure detection support tool to be accepted in a clinical setup, the decision-making process should reduce the interpretation time of the EEG signals such that it can be applied for monitoring. The least requirement for clinical acceptance is a specificity below 5% and sensitivity of 95% and above, and authors in [108] have used a hybrid approach for training and validating their model for efficient seizure detection according to the requirement. For sequential decoding, a hidden Markov model has been used that helps in spatial and temporal decoding of the signal such that it improved the decision making. Stacked denoising Autoencoders has been used for organizing the knowledge obtained and further refining the decision-making approach.

Gaussian Mixture Hidden Markov Model (GMM-HMM) has also been used by Espindola et al. [109] for designing a four-stage patient-specific epileptic seizure prediction system. For dimensionality reduction of features, authors used a hybrid combination of PCA-ICA. Ensemble of neural network has been proposed by Mingyang Li et al. [110] for differentiating between epileptic and normal signals using wavelet-based envelope analysis. The central idea of neural network ensemble is to break down complex problems and transform them into simpler sub-problems. A series of networks formed the ensemble and each was responsible for particular pattern classification. The output from each of the networks was then joined to reach the final prediction. Similar to the ensemble method, a polling-based unsupervised approach related to self-organizing maps has been used by Kitano et al. [111] for seizure prediction. The ensemble method in form of the random forest has been used by Sharaf et al. [112] for an intelligent computer-aided method. The features extracted using tunable Q-wavelet have been optimized into a compact set of features by firefly optimization before being transferred to the ensemble classifier. Apart from ensemble neural networks and random forest, ensemble stacking classification has been used by Rahman et al. [113] for refining the classification accuracy of seizure detection.

The core idea generally assumed while designing a traditional method for seizure detection is that there are enough training samples and both training and test have similar distribution of data. But seldom do these criteria get satisfied. Hence, transfer learning is applied by authors [114] to address this problem. They have used E TTL-

TSK-FS with two transfer learning mechanisms for resolving the issue and enhancing the performance of seizure detection. The problem of class imbalance in EEG data has also been addressed by Asif et al. [115] in their work. The authors have highlighted two sampling techniques that can be applied to handle the class imbalance problem. Random under-sampling or SMOTE could be used to down-sample or up-sample the EEG data with class imbalance.

2.5 Graph-based Methods

Spatio-temporal synchronization pattern of scalp EEG signals obtained with the help of theoretic spectral graph features has been used for proposing an operative multivariate seizure detection module that would be able to identify seizure onset in real-time. Fan and Chou [116] in their work have used a complex network structure of spectral graph to present the reappearance of signal pattern such that the temporal synchronization could be quantified. Moreover, a separate control chart has been used in their work for extracted features to maintain the shift in the pattern when signals change from normal to ictal state. The graph-theoretic features have been able to detect substantial changes in the temporal synchronization of the EEG signal, hence enabling a patient-specific seizure detection unit that presented commendable sensitivity and low average latency helpful in real-time detection. Chaos and spectral graph theory have been used for depicting the temporal subtleties of the EEG signals. A sliding window has been used [116] for segmentation of the scalp signals which is followed by a mapping function representing the state space of each segmented EEG system. Each state space has its state space trajectory that records the changes in the state space over time. Patterns that occurred repetitively (recurrence pattern) have been represented with the help of neighborhood relationships between system states using a recurrence plot (RP).

Each of the recurrence plots is re-analyzed before the construction of the recurrence network (RN) through adjacency matrices. Eventually, the authors used the spectral graph theory for extraction of the global topological features from the recurrence network and followed it with a conservative approach of recurrence quantification analysis (RQA) for comparing the spectral features. In [116], two separate models have been used, for Model I an extension of univariate time series has been applied in form of multivariate generalization of recurrence plot for presenting the n-dimensional system. The time delay factor has not been considered for Model I. While in Model II, the state space trajectory of each EEG segment is reconstructed using the time delayed embedding method. Different recurrence quantification analysis and graph-theoretic

features are extracted from the recurrence plot of both the models. To analyze the impact of the recurrence network, distance matrices in unthresholded RN and binary matrices in thresholded RN are studied using eigen decomposition. This helped authors in understanding information quality and preservation of relevant information required for developing an efficient epileptic seizure detection system.

To study the pattern, characteristics and dependencies of different regions of the brain Akbarian and Erfanian [117], studied the functional brain connectivity (FBC) for the statistical dependencies and effective brain connectivity (EBC) for explicit directional effects to develop a reliable seizure detection system. Different modular networks have been used MLMN that combined EBC classification results at different frequencies, while MENN applied three EBC results at a specific frequency and lastly, MFNN that used seven different frequencies to combine the EBC classification results. The authors used generalized partial directed coherence, directed coherence, and directed transfer function for studying the effective brain connectivity. To understand the dynamics of the brain, the importance of structural knowledge and its functional relationship with different areas is highlighted as it plays a vital role in designing an efficient seizure detection unit. Based on these principles, the authors used brain connectivity to extract information about changes that take place in different frequencies during an epileptic attack and combined them with modular networks to achieve maximum seizure detection accuracy. A blend of different local and global graph theory measures has been considered as features and they signify the nodal properties of effective brain connectivity.

Autoencoder has been used for mapping and reducing the dimension of the extracted features. The binary softmax classifier is used to classify the EEG signals and the results are combined according to different rules to attain different modular network structures. Dependencies between network architectures and their components can be analyzed using effective connectivity and this idea has been used in [117] to study the brain connections and relation between neurons during an epileptic seizure attack. The linear multivariate autoregressive model has been used for defining the regional dependencies of the brain with the Akaike information criterion (AIC) for selecting the modular network. Another highlight of the work [117] lies in the usage of modularity classification where the classification takes place through the simpler tasks. Multiple binary classifiers are trained before results are combined according to specific rules for reaching the final classified result. The results presented showed a multi-level modular

network or MLMN to achieve the highest mean accuracy of 99.43% for classifying epileptic seizure signals.

In recent years complex graph structures have been employed for characterizing EEG signals and developing automated seizure detection systems. As existing systems fail to avoid intra-class variance because of phase shift, Wang et al. [118] in their work used proposed a complicated system with near to perfect data alignment based on frequency domain representation. The authors proposed the feature extraction process using a deep learning model called Sequential graph convolutional network (SGCN). The method is a combination of sequential convolution incorporated within graph neural network that plays a key role in information preserving. Wide-ranging experimental demonstrations have brought forward its efficacy and dependability. As the authors have used fast Fourier transformation, the obtained features are aligned perfectly and intra-class variance is avoided that occurs due to phase shift of the signal. As graph neural network specifically treats every mode as homogeneous, authors proposed SGCN that helped in retaining the sequential characteristics of the EEG signals. Apart from that, SGCN has the capability of learning the parameters and analyzing the contribution of each node present in the graph that would eventually enhance the performance of classification.

2.6 Hardware-based Seizure Detection Systems

An automated and transportable seizure detection system is suitable for patients with epilepsy. To incorporate effective training and accurate seizure detection ability on a chip, Feng et al. [119] in their work presented a VLSI design that has been constructed around SVM. The design contained two modules – a module extraction of feature and another for EEG signal classification using SVM. Daubechies wavelet up to the third level has been used for extracting relevant time-frequency features that reflected the non-stationary property of the EEG signal. The modified sequential minimal optimization algorithm has been combined with a table-driven-based Gaussian kernel to design an efficient on-chip strategy. Authors have used Altera Cyclone II FPGA for corroboration of the proposed design using two freely available datasets. Their obtained results have shown improved detection accuracy with the VLSI-based seizure detection system. The seizure detection architecture proposed by the authors consisted of the following, an FE module, a DDR2 SDRAM Controller module, and an SVM-based classification module. The long EEG recordings have been stored using an off-chip SDRAM while the controller unit is responsible for communicating between the

SDRAM and the system. The feature extraction module processes these large amounts of EEG recordings to extract the required features. The signal is broken down up to the third level and into four sub-bands using Daubechies wavelet and the MAV and VAR of the coefficients are obtained that produced the 8-dimensional feature vector. The support vector machine used this 8-dimensional feature for training the features and detecting seizures. The SVM classifies the onset of seizure along with seizure-free signals.

Biomedical research is significantly directing its attention on developing energy-efficient both invasive and non-invasive real-time integrated seizure detection circuits. Sayeed et al. [22] proposed an implantable hyper-synchronous signal detection circuit that has signal rejection capability. The detection unit was responsible for hyper-synchronous pulses and constantly monitored the neuronal activity via signals. This was done to identify the pulse generated during a seizure onset. When pulses surpassed the fixed threshold value, the event was marked as a seizure. The authors validated their proposed approach with the help of Simulink. The seizure rejection capability of the method reduced the false detection rate and also the power consumption was seen to be reduced by 12%. The number of hyper-synchronous pulses present in the EEG data has been used as the focal point for detecting the onset of a seizure. The signal rejection algorithm used by the authors removed unwanted signals such that the hypersynchronous pulses could be identified correctly once they crossed the designated threshold mark. This rejection algorithm thus helped in reducing the false detection rate. As the number of circuits used in developing the detection unit is limited comprising of an amplifier, modulator, voltage level detector and high-pass filter. Therefore, the power consumption of the system is low, making the detection unit energy efficient.

In another of their work, Sayeed et al. [120] proposed a seizure detection system incorporating the ideas of the IoT framework. The basic detection system is comprised of EEG signal decomposing and feature extraction with the help of statistical features and Hjorth parameters along with a deep neural network (DNN) classifier. The hardware-in-loop approach has been used to implement the archetype of the proposed Neuro-Detect model. According to the findings by the authors, the Hjorth parameter showed substantial variance in the values obtained from different stages of the EEG signals. High accuracy has been seen while classifying between the normal and ictal phases of the EEG signal. With the help of a deep neural network, the authors have

been able to quantify the complexity of the EEG signal as it plays a crucial role in characterizing the signal. Also, the data and different state of the EEG signal has been uploaded in the cloud thus combining the essence of IoT and features of the cloud. Following their previous works, authors made advancements by designing an automated system that has a drug delivery system to control seizures [121]. Their proposed approach was capable of detecting a seizure and then injecting an anti-convulsant drug that would help in overturning the seizure attack.

The first stage involves the detection unit that detects seizures from EEG recordings which are followed by the second stage, the release of drug in the specific area of seizure occurrence. System-level simulation has been performed by authors to validate their proposed method. The hardware used has been minimal thus leading to reduced power consumption. The system provided the facility to be used as either non-invasive (wearable) approach or invasive (implantable) approach or even a combination of both. The central control system contained both detector and drug delivery mechanisms. The detection circuitry monitored the EEG signals by maintaining a particular threshold for the pulse and signals crossing the threshold, marking the onset of a seizure event. The drug release mechanism has been a combination of an open-loop and closed-loop system. The open-loop system has been responsible for the release of drug at steady intervals while the anticonvulsant drug is injected only once by the closed-loop system into the seizure onset area.

To develop low-cost wearable and portable devices, wireless body sensors have been designed and deployed in the health sector for the automatic detection of epileptic seizures. Although these body sensors present an attractive solution but the primary hurdle lies in developing sensors that are energy efficient. To address this problem, Alhassan et al. [122] in their work have proposed energy-efficient non-invasive wireless body sensors for epilepsy seizure detection. The authors have segmented the EEG signals and then used Haar wavelet for extracting the local features from the signals. The decomposed signal has been used for classification and if the incidence of seizure is noted in the recordings, a notification is generated for the remote server via body sensors. The body sensors are responsible for upholding the result of classification instead of the remote server, thus reducing energy consumption. The results presented by the authors for a 10sec segment of EEG signal show a sensitivity of 97% and 46% saving of energy by the sensors in comparison to when raw EEG recordings are

streamed to the remote server. An open-source simulator, Avrora has been used by the authors for the embedded programs of the sensors.

The inclusion of cloud-related biomedical implants and sensors has enriched the mobile healthcare sector, making it an emerging field of innovative research. With this background, Qaisar et al. [123] used level-crossing sampling and adaptive-rate processing based state-of-the-art seizure detection method. The proposed approach was capable of reducing the computational complexity along with the energy required for the transmission of data and other activities. A level-crossing analog-to-digital converter (LCADC) has been used to obtain the EEG signals, followed by an activity selection algorithm that decided the active region of the signal. This technique helped in effectively maneuvering the adaptive rates – denoising, decomposition of the signal and dimension reduction. It helped the authors in reducing the samples obtained for verifying the proposed method, eventually bringing down the computational complexity of the proposed method. Transmission power, load of the cloud-based classifier and consumption of bandwidth used gets visible reduction with commendable accuracy in epileptic seizure detection.

Apart from wearable sensors, FPGA has been used by authors for designing hardware-based automated epilepsy seizure detection systems. Saric et al. [124] in their work used an FPGA-based feed-forward multi-layer neural network for classifying epileptic seizures. Time-frequency analysis of the EEG signals along with continuous wavelet transformation and statistical analysis has been performed to obtain the relevant features. The authors used a separate set for testing the detection performance of the model and used VHDL for implementing their proposed ANN model on the FPGA. The testing results of the hardware model asserted that it could be used for building the basic design of an application-specific integrated circuit. Their proposed architecture of the seizure detection system has been implemented using the Field Programmable Gate Array Altera D2-115 Cyclone IV E series board. As FPGA architecture is reprogrammable, it allows a degree of freedom in executing complex circuits through the presence of configurable logic blocks and programmable interconnections. Also, FPGAs come with improved on-chip learning properties and added facility of mapping properties on new FPGAs thus surpassing the microcontrollers that are also programmable circuits. This facilitates chip development in a much cost-effective way for large production required in the biomedical field for real-time diagnosis. As VHDL

permits access to internal variables and subcomponents, there is increased reliability and more control over different mathematical operations.

Such reconfigurable FPGA has been used for executing linear binary support vector-based method for detecting epileptic seizures by Rafiammal et al. [125]. The authors claimed their proposed design to use a lesser number of resources for current hardware-based detection units. A Zynq board -ZC 706 FPGA has been used along with Vivado high-level synthesis software for designing the integrated chip. Both training and testing phases have been implemented in the FPGA for analyzing the efficacy of their method. The authors used clock pulse and accordingly divided the EEG data into 20sec segments for each clock pulse. A look-up table or LUT has been used for storing the programming logic such that it can execute the working algorithm responsible for the classification of EEG signals. The results obtained by the authors showed satisfactory outcomes such that it can be considered to be implemented in a real-life situation.

After studying all the above-mentioned techniques and applications it is observed that there is still a need for improvement regarding performance and alarming situations of pediatric epileptic seizure. Various approaches for detecting and predicting epileptic seizures have been used over the years. Few of the recent studies in traditional as well as deep learning methods have been summarized in the Tables 2.1 and 2.2. However, there is no performance evaluation system that has been recognized as a standard. Furthermore, the seizure detection accuracy of these various methods should be based on the dataset that the researchers are using, as differences in the dataset might have a substantial impact on the method's output.

Table 2.1 Traditional classifiers-based approaches for pediatric epileptic seizure detection

Authors	Year	Methods	Limitations
Shoeb [145]	2009	Spectral feature, SVM	Patient-specific
Bhattacharya and Pachori [36]	2017	EWT, Random Forest	Channel specific and short duration of EEG recording
Bonello et al. [49]	2018	Power spectral density, SVM	Patient-specific data labels

Hameed et al. [34]	2018	Principal dynamic modes	Restricted to two lobes of the brain
Kaleem et al. [25]	2018	DWT, kNN, SVM	Short EEG segments
Rukhsar et al. [59]	2019	Statistical process control	Inter ictal segments considered
Jiang et al. [33]	2020	Geometric decomposition	Only 5 channels have been considered
Akbarian and Erfanian [117]	2020	Graph theory	Variation of network topology
Yadav and Sharma [74]	2021	Shallow neural network	Single EEG channel and patient specific
Peng et al. [35]	2021	Sparse matrix representation	Channels selected according to variance

Table 2.2 Deep learning-based approaches for pediatric epilepsy seizure detection

Authors	Year	Methods	Limitations
Tsiouris et al. [86]	2018	LSTM	Limited preictal segment, Patient-specific
Wei et al. [100]	2019	CNN	Patient-specific approach
Thara et al. [99]	2019	Stacked Bi-LSTM	Small dataset
Hossain et al. [97]	2019	CNN	Random selection of patient and data division

Hu et al. [104]	2020	Bi-LSTM	Frequency domain-based product function
Abiyev et al. [78]	2020	Deep CNN	High rate of false alarm
Usman et al. [79]	2020	CNN	Patient-specific prediction
Li et al. [105]	2020	CNN-Nested LSTM	High false detection rate
Gomez et al. [91]	2020	CNN	Short recording segments, Patient specific
Wang et al. [118]	2021	1D-CNN	Random selection and data augmentation

Therefore, after studying prior works a generalized view regarding the drawbacks can be inferred as follows –

- Most of the prior works are patient-specific.
- Arbitrary channel selection leading to channel-specific models.
- The use of ictal segment is limited.
- Random selection of data for model training.
- Arbitrary selection of brain region.

Hence in the following works an attempt has been made to provide an improved method for pediatric epileptic seizure detection that has addressed few of the shortcomings if not all with realization and performance analysis. The present works have used generalized approach in place of patient-specific approach, also the works are channel independent, there is no arbitrary selection of channels hence all the brain regions have been considered. Also, while using the EEG recordings, as ictal segments have short duration careful selection has been done such that there is semblance between different segments.

2.7 Conclusion

Over the years, seizure detection with the aid of different machine learning techniques have garnered attention and it continues to the present day. As EEG signals are known to be challenging due their inherent property of unpredictability, hence researches have used more than one approach to address the problems surrounding seizure detection using electroencephalogram signals. Be it statistical approaches to extract important pertinent to EEG signals or referring different traditional classifiers, authors have used far and wide methods for the purpose of seizure detection. With gradual advancement in research, hybrid as well as deep learning techniques have been used that helped in reducing the additional step of feature extraction. Furthermore, researchers have been mindful in designing portable hardware units that would work towards the purpose of detecting seizure effectively in patients suffering from epilepsy.

Chapter 3: A Generalized Pediatric Epileptic Seizure Detection System using Wavelet Transform and Artificial Neural Network

In this chapter, a time-domain implementation has been proposed for seizure recognition using discrete wavelet transformation and an artificial neural network. The proposed method emphasizes pediatric epileptic seizures that pose a problem during detection. A generalized approach has been used so that the method is able to detect every epileptic conditions. Also, the proposed method is designed such that it considers all the EEG recording channels during detection as the epileptic condition can manifest at a different location and can be recorded across multiple channels in both hemispheres of the brain. Different families of wavelets have been used and the appropriate features from EEG signals are chosen to find a suitable pattern. The extracted features are then used in the traditional artificial neural network classifier to detect between non-seizure and seizure signals. For convenient recognition and monitoring of pediatric epilepsy, the suggested method has been implemented as a hardware setup utilizing MATLAB/SIMULINK and Arduino. Sym4 wavelet reached the highest accuracy of 95.3%. As a result, it is worth considering for real-time application in hospitals since it is effective and robust, and it may be used to monitor epileptic seizure in pediatric patients.

3.1 Techniques Used

3.1.1 Discrete Wavelet Transformation (DWT)

Continuous wavelet transform (CWT) and discrete wavelet transform (DWT) are the two different types of wavelet transforms. In DWT, the input signal is broken down into sub-levels with the help of filters. When the signal is decomposed in DWT, a set of mutually orthogonal wavelet basis functions is formed. These basis functions are spatially located and are non-zero only over a part of the total signal [36]. Moreover, the wavelet functions are translated, dilated and scaled over one common function, also identified as the mother wavelet. Apart from this, DWT is invertible, thus the decomposed signal can be recomposed back to the original signal from its wavelet representation. In discrete wavelet transform, there is a set of transforms and each of the transformations has its own set of basis functions. The elementary idea that governs the decomposition and reconstruction of a signal is filtering and the use of down

sampling and up sampling [126]. In wavelet decompositions, the decomposed signals are arranged hierarchically as seen in Fig. 3.1. The levels of decomposition depend on the signal used and the cut-off frequency required by the signal. Convolution is the mathematical operation that is used in the filter banks for filtering the signal. A simple filter bank consists of two filters – a lowpass and a high pass filter. These filters are also known as analysis filters. When these filters are used for combining or reconstructing the signals, they are known as synthesis filters. The signals are either down-sampled or up-sampled depending upon the type of filtering. When analysis filters are used the signal is down-sampled while in the synthesis filter bank, the signal is up-sampled. One half of the signal gets rejected following the Nyquist rule when the signal is passed through the low-pass ($h(n)$) or half band filter [126]. Usually, the original signal is first passed through a high-pass ($g(n)$) filter followed by a low-pass filter. The scaling equation of discrete wavelet transformation for a particular signal contains an approximate coefficient and detailed coefficient. The co-efficient of filter banks corresponds to wavelet coefficient and scaling,

$$g[n] = (-1)^n h[L - n], n = 0, 1, \dots, L - 1 \quad (3.1)$$

where, L represent the filter length.

Fig.3.1 Wavelet decomposition [126].

The wavelet $\psi(t)$ and scaling $\varphi(t)$ is represented as,

$$\varphi(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{L-1} h(n)\varphi(2t - n) \quad (3.2)$$

$$\psi(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{L-1} g(n)\varphi(2t - n) \quad (3.3)$$

Decomposition of the signal using discrete wavelet transform can be carried out using different families of wavelets. The most famous family of wavelets is the Daubechies' wavelet developed by the well-known Belgian physicist Ingrid Daubechies [126]. Four families of wavelets have been used for the decomposition of the electroencephalogram signals. They are Daubechies, Coiflets, Symlets and Biorthogonal wavelets. The most well-known wavelet is Daubechies' wavelet, which was created by Belgian scientist Ingrid Daubechies. These wavelets have a maximum number of vanishing moments and are orthogonal. There are various forms of wavelets in the Daubechies wavelet family, such as DB1, DB2, DB4, and so on. The basis function is written as,

$$f(x) = \sum_m f_{mn}\psi_{mn}(x) \quad (3.4)$$

$$f_{mn} = \int f(x)\psi_{mn}(x)dx \quad (3.5)$$

The wavelets belonging to the Symlet family are usually orthogonal, symmetrical, and in the order of N. They are in agreement with the Daubechies wavelet with minor variation. The properties of Symlet and Daubechies are quite similar to one another. Characteristics of linear phase are present in the Bi-orthogonal wavelets which is useful for signal and image reconstruction. In this type of wavelet, two wavelets are used for the decomposition and reconstruction of the original signal. Lastly, the Coiflet family of wavelets have both 2N and 2N-1 moments equal to 0. The support length is 6N-1 and like Daubechies wavelets, they are symmetrical.

3.1.2 Artificial Neural Network

Although ANN resembles the nervous system but is built around on mathematical formulae and inferences. [127]. The neurons, or more specifically the artificial neurons, also known as nodes, are a crucial component of the neural network architecture. The actual synapses are depicted as an effect of various input signals with connection weights, while the transfer function depicts the neuron's non-linear characteristics. Figure 3.2 depicts the basic construction of an artificial neural network. The summation of weighted input is used to calculate the neuron's impulse, which is then adjusted using the transfer function [128]. The efficacy of neural learning is achieved by varying and altering weights in accordance with the chosen learning algorithm. The output of an artificial neural network is calculated as,

$$O = f(net) = f\left(\sum_{j=1}^n w_j x_j\right) \quad (3.6)$$

where, transfer function is represented as f , and scalar product of input x_j and weight w_j gives the output of the network [128]. The activation function of a neuron in a particular layer can be presented as,

$$a_j^l = f(\sum_k w_{jk}^l a_k^{l-1} + b_j^l) \quad (3.7)$$

where, a_j^l is the activation function of the j^{th} neuron in the l^{th} layer of the network, w and b represents weight and bias respectively. The weighted input to neuron in layer l is calculated as,

$$z^l = w^l a^{l-1} + b^l \quad (3.8)$$

It can also be written as, $a^l = f(z^l)$ and $z_j^l = (\sum_k w_{jk}^l a_k^{l-1} + b_j^l)$.

Fig.3.2. Elementary structure of an artificial neural network [127].

Another multi-layered technique of the neural network is backward propagation of error or commonly known as backpropagation. In this approach, the errors calculated are propagated backward [128]. The backpropagation algorithm holds the core of neural network training. The method helps in fine-tuning of weights of a neural network by using the error obtained in the preceding epoch. This approach helps in the appropriate tuning of the weights associated with the network and also helps in reducing error rates, thus making the neural network model more dependable and generalized. Backpropagation helps in understanding the effects of changing weights and biases and their direct impact on the cost function. The error function is written as,

$$\delta_j^l = \frac{\partial C}{\partial z_j^l} \quad (3.9)$$

where, C is the cost function associated with the neural network.

The equations associated with backpropagation are mentioned as follows,

Error equation in the output layer,

$$\delta^L = \nabla_a C \odot f'(z^L) \quad (3.10)$$

where, $\nabla_a C$ signifies the cost function rate with respect to the output activations.

Error equation in terms of error in the next layer,

$$\delta^l = ((w^{l+1})^T \delta^{l+1}) \odot f'(z^l) \quad (3.11)$$

Cost function with respect to bias of the neural network,

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial b_j^l} = \delta_j^l \quad (3.12)$$

Cost function with respect to weight of the neural network,

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial w_{jk}^l} = a_k^{l-1} \delta_j^l \quad (3.13)$$

3.2 Proposed Methodology

The proposed seizure detection architecture can be divided as – acquisition of EEG signals, feature extraction using discrete wavelet transform and decision making using an artificial neural network. The EEG signals are obtained from non-invasive scalp recordings of pediatric patients. After that, useful features are extracted that can be used to distinguish seizure and non-seizure phases. The classification is based on the features acquired. To analyze the performance of the classifier, the trained unit is validated. The prior mentioned steps are depicted in Fig.3.3.

3.2.1 Dataset Description

The pediatric dataset used in this present work belonged to the Children’s Hospital Boston Massachusetts Institute of Technology (CHB-MIT). Non-invasive recordings (scalp) of patients between 1.5 years to 15years with past incidents of intractable seizure are present in the database. Specific annotations related to the onset of the seizure and its duration are mentioned with the recordings. For each patient, the number of seizures varied between a minimum of one to a maximum of four. 10-20 international system of electrode placement has been followed while recording the EEG signals and the sampling frequency is 256Hz with 16-bit resolution. During the seizure onset, paroxysmal burst is present in different frontal, posterior, and central channels. Also, the EEG signals are not devoid of artifacts such as head, eye, and body movements. The CHB-MIT dataset is available online at the Physionet website [129].

Fig.3.3 Diagrammatic representation of the proposed method.

3.2.2 Feature Extraction using Wavelet

When there is a synaptic exchange in the cerebral cortex between dendrites of many pyramidal neurons, there is a flow of current which is measured by the electroencephalogram signal. EEG signals consist of frequency content that can reach up to 300Hz. The CHB-MIT dataset comprised of neural activities recorded from 23 electrode channels placed in both hemispheres of the brain. As EEG signals frequently contain artifacts in form of eye, and body movements, thus different filters in form of low pass and high pass filters are used to remove these unwanted artifacts. A low pass filter has been used to remove any noise in the range of 50-70Hz while a high pass filter

eliminated low-frequency components from the EEG signals. To remove the artifacts, only a signal processing procedure has been used. For extracting the features, a multi-resolution method of WT has been used by the proposed method. The EEG signal has been divided into different sub-levels by discrete wavelet transformation with a series of filter banks. When a signal is decomposed, the original EEG signal is broken into various sub-levels. Firstly, the signal passes through a filter bank of low-pass and high-pass filters. Detailed coefficients (cD1) and approximation co-efficient (cA1) is generated as the output of the first level decomposition. The frequency of the signal is represented in the form of the coefficients. As this is an iterative process, the signal is further broken down such that the following levels of cD2, cA2, cD3, cA3, etc., can be achieved. With discrete wavelet transformation, the time resolution is halved while the frequency resolution is doubled.

3.2.3 Seizure Detection using Artificial Neural Network

A traditional artificial neural network has been used for classification of EEG signals. As a neural network is comprised of different parameters, hence tuning of those parameters is an important aspect required to design an optimal artificial neural network. The following list of parameters have been tuned:

(a) Normalization: A step that is applied prior to other phases, to scale the data such that a single column of data cannot employ impact over others because of range differences. The range between $[-1, 1]$ has been used for normalization of the data.

(b) Weight initialization: Nguyen-Widrow method has been used to adjust the weight and bias values for even distribution of neurons and reducing training time of the neural network. Large starting weights likely to lead to network saturation, whereas lower beginning weights promote delayed learning. As a result, arbitrary initialization of 0.5 to +0.5 or 1 to +1 have been chosen for weights and biases. Although for tan-sig the range differs slightly, from -2 to +2.

The steps in the Nguyen-Widrow algorithm as follows:

Step 1: The initial setting is as follows:

N denoted input components

P denoted hidden components

β stands for the scaling factor $= 0.7(P)^{1/N} = 0.7\sqrt[N]{P}$

Step 2: Steps (2) – (6) have been repeated for P where $J = 1, \dots, P$

Step 3: For $I = 1$ to N; V_{IJ} = arbitrary number between -2 and 2

Step 4: $\|V_{ij}\|$ is obtained.

Step 5: Weights of N or input units are re-initialized.

Step 6: Initialization of bias: V_{Oj} = arbitrary numbers between the scaling factor ($-\beta$ and β).

(c) Epochs and layers: The total number of times a learning algorithm uses the entire dataset. Epoch number is conservatively maintained big since it aids the algorithm in minimizing error. Since the data size is huge, epoch has been set at 500. There is no set rule for defining layers and neurons in each layer of a NN. It usually relies on trial and error with various network settings, with a bit of intuition. Before the final acceptable architecture, many network configurations with variation in layers and neurons have been trained. The final design is a three-layered network with thirty neurons in the two hidden levels and only one neuron as the output.

The EEG recordings tend to generate large volume of data and the proposed work focused on a generalized approach where recordings from each patient have been consolidated together. Thus, increasing the volume of data many-fold. To speed up training of the model, a simple neural network structure has been used. Moreover, the trained network when implemented in the prototype version using a microcontroller, it has been able to provide laudable result in minimum amount of time when tested. Thus, even though a simple architecture has been preferred over more complex structure, the objective of efficient seizure detection has been achieved.

(d) Learning rate: Step size at each repetition that aids a process in achieving convergence with a minimized loss function and the rate usually fixed between 0.1 and 1.0. The learning rate is determined by the gradient of the loss function and is dependent on the optimization approach of the neural network. The learning rate is changed using Levenberg-Marquardt optimization.

(e) Activation function: The layers of the neural network used Tan-sig activation function. While designing the neural network, different activation functions have been tested before zeroing on the specific mentioned activation function. Also, the derivative of the activation function is steeper which means more value can be obtained. This also means that it has a wider range for fast learning and grading which is more efficient. Due to this reason after testing different activation functions, this specific activation function (tan-sig) has been selected.

(f) Training Function: The training function applied to the neural network is Levenberg Marquardt optimization.

The foremost goal for seizure detection was to generate distinct margins between the data with proper class labels while maintaining a cutoff value for generating the features. In this work, for training the neural network model, 90% of the total samples have been used and the rest 10% data has been used to test the proposed model. Different levels of wavelet decomposition have been applied and checked with different network configurations. 750,000 samples have been used in training for level 1 while 84,000 samples have been used for testing. Similarly, in level 2 nearly 379,000 sample points have been used for training and 42,000 sample points for testing. Lastly, for level 3, 189,000 and 21,000 data samples have been used for training and testing respectively. Fig. 3.1 shows the final neural network configuration and the configuration is kept the same for all the families of wavelets used in this work. A 3-layered neural network has been used as the optimal network in this work. Each hidden layer consisted of 30 neurons and tan-sig activation has been used for a total of 500 training iterations across all four wavelets. The 23 inputs represent the 23 EEG electrode channels, and the output layer consists of a single neuron responsible for labeling the signals either into a seizure or non-seizure class. The first layer uses the input and processes it with the neurons in the first hidden layer. The output generated from the first hidden layer is used as the input to the second hidden layer. The neurons of each layer are adjusted using the backpropagation algorithm. The input vector is multiplied by the weight vector followed by a summation of a bias vector. This produces the net value that goes through the non-linear transfer function to produce the output.

3.3 Results

Pediatric epileptic patients have been used to test the classification accuracy of the proposed approach. Raw signals and wavelet decomposed feature extracted signals have been used with varying the level of decomposition, neurons present in each hidden layer, error goal and transfer function. Sensitivity, specificity and accuracy have been used to estimate the classification results which is in agreement with the golden standard followed in different literature. 10-fold CV has been used for validating the trained classifier.

3.3.1 Performance of the Classifier with Raw Signals

Statistical parameters have been used to study the classification competence of the proposed method on raw data in a patient-specific approach. Table 3.1 shows the detection accuracy achieved for each patient. The accuracy varied from 86% to 99%

and the average accuracy is noted to be 85.5%. The specificity varied from 80% to 99% while sensitivity from 85% to 99%. The average specificity and sensitivity of 10 patients are recorded at 83.6% and 87.5% respectively.

Table 3.1 Classification performance of individual patient using raw signals

	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5
Accuracy (%)	94.7	98.7	98.0	93.7	87.9
Specificity (%)	94.0	98.1	97.6	91.6	87.8
Sensitivity (%)	95.3	99.1	98.2	95.9	88.0
Classified	214365	45973	201660	159781	21157
Misclassified	12049	624	4179	7477	2911
	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10
Accuracy (%)	99.7	90.5	93.2	96.3	86.2
Specificity (%)	99.4	92.7	91.4	95.2	79.5
Sensitivity (%)	99.9	88.4	95.2	97.4	96.7
Classified	48985	425831	120797	100581	225515
Misclassified	168	44707	8747	3873	36153

3.3.2 Performance of the Classifier with Processed Signals

The performance of all the wavelet families for different levels of decomposition has been analyzed and compared. Table 3.2 presents the performance metrics of the neural network for different wavelets. Additionally, plots have been provided for all four wavelets such that the accuracy achieved can be analyzed. Daubechies wavelet has the highest accuracy of 94.7 percent for DB8, while Bior 4.4 has the maximum accuracy of 94.2 percent, as seen in Fig. 3.4(b). For the Symlet family, Sym4 has achieved the maximum accuracy of 95.3 percent and finally, as shown in Fig. 3.4, Coif 1 from the Coiflet family recorded the best accuracy of 94.3 percent. Thus, comparing the accuracy of the classifier, Sym4 at level 3 of decomposition attained the highest accuracy. In this work, different network structures for the artificial neural network

have been used before the appropriate and effective configuration is achieved for the proposed method. Table 3.3 records the list of all the network structures that have been simulated. It also presents the accuracy, specificity and sensitivity of all simulated configurations. Fig 3.5 shows the receiver operating curve of each artificial neural network structure and helps in understanding the classification rate based on true positive rate and false-positive rate.

Table 3.2 Performance of the classifier for four wavelet families

Wavelet	Type	Network Configuration and Transfer Function	Accuracy (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)
Daubechies	DB1	30-30-1 Tan-sig	93.7	95.5	92.0
	DB2		94.5	96.2	92.5
	DB4		94.3	95.3	92.2
	DB8		94.7	96.4	92.3
Bi-orthogonal	BIOR1.1		94.0	95.9	91.9
	BIOR3.7		93.0	95.7	91.0
	BIOR4.4		94.2	96.3	92.4
	BIOR6.8		94.0	95.8	91.7
Symlet	SYM1		94.0	95.7	91.6
	SYM2		93.0	95.0	91.6
	SYM4		95.3	97.2	93.5
	SYM8		94.0	95.5	91.8
Coiflet	COIF1		94.3	95.9	92.1
	COIF3		93.4	95.8	91.9
	COIF5		94.2	96.2	92.3

Table 3.3 Performance of different neural network configurations for Sym4 (third level decomposition)

	5-5-1	10-10-1	10-20-1	20-20-1	30-30-1
Accuracy (%)	82.7	85.9	86.3	88.1	95.3
Specificity (%)	81.1	84.1	84.4	86.0	93.5
Sensitivity (%)	84.3	87.8	88.4	90.4	97.2

Chapter 3: A Generalized Pediatric Epileptic Seizure Detection System using Wavelet Transform and Artificial Neural Network

Classified	174637	181415	182362	186113	201005
Misclassified	36573	29795	28848	25097	10205

Fig. 3.4 Performance of all wavelets (a) DB (b) Bi-or (c) Sym (d) Coif for generalized approach.

Fig. 3.5 Receiver operating characteristic curve of different network structure for the Symlet4 wavelet.

3.4 Discussion

A time-domain-based pediatric seizure detection method using discrete wavelet transformation and the artificial neural network has been proposed in this work. As seen in literature, the most preferred choice of wavelet decompositions is Daubechies, but for extracting the necessary features Symlet has been used in this work. Apart from the proposed model, a prototype model has been designed using a microcontroller that is low in power consumption and also compatible to work with a different system. This prototype model would help in building an on-chip detection model for epileptic seizure in the future. The use of a different wavelet family did not pose as a hindrance to extracting relevant features from the raw EEG signals. Classification and channel selection has been done using genetic algorithm-based neural network and CNN by various authors. Additional difficulty met in EEG signals is the disparity in the electrode recording channels. Hence, identifying a specific group of channels for a generalized framework is not suitable. The proposed work is not devoid of limitations and these limitations provide an impetus for future directions. The current idea is not purely hardware-based, and the microcontroller's memory retention capability is limited. Long-hour EEG records were not examined because of this limitation. As a result, creating a full hardware system-on-chip module for pediatric patients would be a future area for refining the work. It would be non-invasive, and it would be capable of detecting seizures in a short amount of time. Another factor to consider when developing a module is its low power consumption and cost-effectiveness, both of which are important in real-world applications.

3.5 Implementation

The proposed method was implemented in MATLAB/SIMULINK and Arduino for convenient identification of epileptic episodes. Fig.3.6 illustrates the enactment of the monitoring system. In this work, the dataset contained EEG records obtained from 23 EEG channels. For extraction of relevant features, discrete wavelet transform has been used and the extracted features are fed to the classifier module. The ANN module is trained with the essential parameters. The result obtained has been labeled as 0 for normal EEG signals and 1 for EEG signals containing seizures. To mark the presence of a seizure attack, an alarm has been designed. The prototype model based on the microcontroller is compatible to work with different sensors and in different environment. Also, power consumption of the prototype model is very low. Due to these aspects, the prototype model can be considered in real situation. As from the view

point of complexity, the complexity of neural network is $T = cA + (n - ni)G$. But as the network deployed will already be a trained network, hence during real time implementation, it will only time to extract the features followed by displaying of the output. As shown in Fig. 3.6, the output of the classification model is connected to Arduino, which raises the warning. The red light implies an epileptic condition, while the green light indicates a normal condition. The patient is in normal state when the green light is on, as shown in Fig. 3.6(b). Similarly, the red light is on in Fig. 3.6(c), indicating that the person is undergoing an epileptic episode. It's a simple approach to keep track of epileptic occurrences.

Fig.3.6 Enactment of the epileptic seizure detection and monitoring system using MATLAB/SIMULINK and Arduino.

3.6 Conclusion

In this approach, an adaptable method for pediatric patients suffering from epilepsy has been forwarded that is designed around wavelet transform for feature extraction and ANN for classification.

- A microcontroller-based implementation has been done for substantiating the detection accuracy in minimum time. The purpose of this enactment is to realize if the prototype model is able to detect presence of seizure in a test sample when given to the trained classifier and how efficiently it is able to generate a warning (light in this case).

The minimum amount of time thus referring to the time it requires when the seizure is detected and the warning light showing red.

- The added advantage of this work is that it contributed in giving satisfactory results for seizure detection in a short amount of time. Hence, the flexibility of the proposed method can be verified in real-world scenarios.
- The archetype circuit is simple, with low power consumption and the microcontroller is compatible with a variety of sensors in different settings.

Chapter 4: Pediatric Epileptic Seizure Detection based on Moving Window Technique

In this chapter test sample method has been proposed for epileptic seizure detection using five different features and four different classifiers. Features from the time domain, frequency domain and time-frequency domain have been used for discerning between normal and seizure recordings. A channel-independent generalized approach has been adopted such that the proposed method is able to sense every epileptic conditions. Four different classifiers namely, DT, ensemble learning, ANN, and RF have been considered and their seizure detection capability has been comprehensively studied. Generally, cross-validation is used for validating the performance of a classifier. But for this proposed work, the test sample method has been considered for determining the efficiency of the four classifiers. A moving window of 1 second has been used to extract suitable feature patterns with DWT, mean, DFT, STD, and energy, from the EEG recordings. These features are then used in the four classifiers to compare the efficacy of seizure detection using the test sample technique. Random forest for the CHB-MIT dataset has shown better performance amid the four classifiers with an accuracy of 91.9%, specificity of 89.7% and sensitivity of 94.1%. A second dataset from the Sleep-Wake-Epilepsy-Center (SWEC) has been used for the corroboration of the suggested approach. As the proposed approach is neither channel or patient-specific and presented with a promising detection accuracy, hence it can be used as an improved approach for detecting seizures that accompany during epilepsy attacks.

4.1. Techniques Used

4.1.1. Decision Tree

When it comes to classifying data or understanding a hidden pattern from a given collection of data, the decision tree is taken into consideration as one among the few widely used classification methods. A DT contains a set of nodes with one root node and the rest of the nodes known as internal and leaf nodes. The decision tree's last layer is made up of leaf nodes that usually displays the target value of a specific class. The main backbone for constructing a decision tree is through the repetitive splitting of the nodes at each level based on the splitting criteria. The sequential phases of split and grow continues until a stopping criterion is encountered [130]. The different criteria can be expressed mathematically as follows,

$$InformationGain(a_i, S) = Entropy(y, S) - \sum_{v_{i,j} \in dom(a_i)} \frac{|\sigma_{a_i=v_{i,j}} S|}{|S|} \cdot Entropy(y, \sigma_{a_i=v_{i,j}} S) \quad (4.1)$$

$$where, Entropy(y, S) = \sum_{c_j \in dom(y)} \frac{|\sigma_{y=c_j} S|}{|S|} \cdot \log_2 \frac{|\sigma_{y=c_j} S|}{|S|} \quad (4.2)$$

$$Gini(y, S) = 1 - \sum_{c_j \in dom(y)} \left(\frac{|\sigma_{y=c_j} S|}{|S|} \right)^2 \quad (4.3)$$

The evaluation criterion is written as,

$$GiniGain(a_i, S) = Gini(y, S) - \sum_{v_{i,j} \in dom(a_i)} \frac{|\sigma_{a_i=v_{i,j}} S|}{|S|} \cdot Gini(y, \sigma_{a_i=v_{i,j}} S) \quad (4.4)$$

$$Gain\ Ratio(a_i, S) = \frac{InformationGain(a_i, S)}{Entropy(a_i, S)} \quad (4.5)$$

4.1.2. Ensemble Learning

Ensemble learning is a combination of different learning machines or classifiers that in a certain way combine all algorithms to generate more accurate and reliable results [131]. The principle of the Condorcet jury theorem can be used as a theoretical base for ensemble learning. In ensemble methodology, an inducer is also known as a strong learner that is randomly well correlated with the actual classification of the labeled training set. While a weak learner is to some extent correlated to the true classification. The idea of ensemble learning dates back to the late seventies when Tukey brought forward the idea of joining two linear regression models [132]. Boosting is one of the most prominent model-guided methods for selecting instances. It is also known as adaptive resampling that helps by running the weak learner repeatedly to enhance the performance. The main aim behind the development of AdaBoost is to identify patterns among instances that are difficult to detect. Mathematically the classification of instance by AdaBoost can be written as:

$$H(x) = sign(\sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t \cdot M_t(x)) \quad (4.6)$$

where, M_t represents the classifiers while α_t is the individual weight of each classifier. Apart from the boosting algorithm, one of the independent methods most commonly used is bagging or bootstrap aggregating [132]. Bagging helps in increasing accuracy by forming a combined classifier that integrated the output of every classifier into a single prediction.

4.1.3. Random Forest

Random forest is a variant of ensemble learning that use several decision trees for classification and regression. The presence of permutation in the training phase distinguishes the random forest approach from the others. Generally, with a random selection of important features, the bagging method is used to classify data in a random forest. Random forest classifier exhibits a certain amount of randomness in selecting the subset and features for the nodes of each tree. The Gini index is used as a criterion for separating data in the random forest. Breiman showed that combining more than one estimator into an ensemble can result in a significant increase in accuracy. He presented it both theoretically and empirically that normal models have low expected generalization error than the combined model. Breiman [134] in his paper combined random subset selection with bagging at each node to inject the essence of randomness and build a more effective classifier that is capable of addressing any given problem. In addition, the random forest gives importance to variables that would not only help in developing an accurate model but will also play a significant part in prediction [133].

4.2. Proposed Methodology

4.2.1. Dataset Description

The pediatric dataset used in this present work belonged to the CHB-MIT dataset [129] and a detailed description of the dataset has been provided in Chapter 3. The second dataset used in the proposed work belonged to the Sleep-Wake-Epilepsy-Center (SWEC) [135]. The database comprised of 100 seizures from 99 recordings belonging to a total of 16 patients. The dataset contained iEEG signals that have been recorded using strip, depth, and grid electrodes [136]. Reference electrode of Fz and Cz has been used according to the international 10/20 electrode position. During recording, the sampling frequency has been 512Hz and for filtering the signals, a fourth-order Butterworth filter has been used. The EEG recordings contained interictal and postictal segments, each of 3 minutes while ictal segments between 10s and 1002s in between.

4.2.2. Feature Extraction using Moving Window Technique

As extracting pertinent features is essential for EEG signals classification accuracy, feature extraction is no exception in this work. These substantial features contribute to distinguishing between non-seizure and seizure phases. The main reason behind extracting the features is to learn the pertinent characteristics of the electroencephalogram signals. This step helps in distinguishing from unnecessary content present in the signal and also making it more compact and amenable for further

interpretation by machine or machine learning algorithms. In this segment, different features like STD, DFT [139], mean, (DWT) [138], and energy [137], have been extracted from the original EEG recording using a moving window of 1 second (overlapped). Features from different domains have been used to understand and extract statistical information, spectral estimation and time-frequency changes related to the EEG signals during a seizure attack. The moving distance of the window that is moved over the signal is equal to its width. The main reason behind using a moving window with a specific time period is to statistically synthesize the data and analyze the dynamic aspect of the EEG signal throughout that time. EEG signals are infamous for their variability, thus displaying a wide range of changes within a given time period. To address this issue, the moving window technique has been applied such that subtle changes with respect to time can be identified. These changes have been analyzed with the inclusion of different features that have been extracted over the given time frame of the moving window. The justification behind using a 1sec window is to keep resemblance with the sampling frequency of 256Hz of the original signal. Therefore, as the 1sec moving window shifts over the signal, it contained 256 samples. Fig.4.1 demonstrates the use of a moving window for extracting the feature mean from the EEG signal. Fig.4.1 (a) presents the signal from one electrode or channel with more than one window, each encompassing 256 samples. The three different colors represent the three windows with samples from 1 to 256, 2 to 257 and 3 to 258. Fig.4.1 (b) shows that before the first sample is generated, mean feature of the first 256 samples is of zero magnitudes. In Fig.4.1 (b), the mean from the first window of 256 samples is generated as the 257th sample. The next sample is generated as the window slides over i.e., from 2 to 257 samples. In this similar method, the window slides over the entire length of the signal to obtain the mean value from all of 23 channels. The moving window approach was followed in the similar fashion to extract features for the other four remaining techniques.

Fig. 4.1 Overlapping moving window technique to extract feature from EEG signals.

4.2.3. Seizure Detection using Learning Techniques

The seizure detection model based on moving window technique is intended such that it could proficiently discern a seizure instance from a non-seizure period. In this work, tree-based (decision tree) and boosted ensemble classifier (ensemble learning) have been considered. Apart from that, a classical learning approach based on ANN and random forest has been considered as it has shown efficacy in working with imbalanced data. Supervised machine learning is capable of learning the mapping between the input and the output, and is also able to predict the outcome of the system when given new inputs. As the end goal of the work is to discern between non-seizure and seizure segments present in EEG signals instead of learning patterns that might be present, hence a supervised learning approach has been taken where specific data label is present that helped in discerning the signals. Also, with presence of specific data labels, using supervised learning helped in achieving accurate results as the automated model is pre-trained with snippets of signals that it can encounter in future. As a test sample approach has been adopted in the proposed work, therefore the proposed method is trained first followed by testing of the trained module with previously unseen data. To scrutinize thoroughly the seizure discerning accuracy of the applied classifiers, entirely changed recordings have been used in the working phases. 844,336 samples constituted the seizure segment while 844,439 samples made up the non-seizure segment, which led to the final number of working samples to be 1,688,775. The training module used 70% of the total working samples, whereas the testing module used 30%. A random or

arbitrary sample division approach was used to divide the data sample and hence the total number of samples that comprised the training module was 1,178,599, while the testing module included 505,097.

4.2.3.1. Training Module

The training framework is comprised of the basic phase of data collection, which in this work is a scalp electroencephalogram dataset and a second dataset containing invasive intracranial EEG (iEEG) signals. Extraction of appropriate features is the succeeding step. A moving window of 1 second has been used for feature mining. The processed signals are then used to train each classifier (DT, ANN, ensemble learning, and RF) so that they can identify specifically non-seizure and seizure phases. Fig.4.2 presents the diagrammatic representation of the proposed method. Prior to establishing the final design, each learning framework (classifier) has been tested with several settings and specifications. In this work, while designing the model for ANN different structural configurations have been tried and tested before zeroing on the mentioned structure. Inclusion of added hidden layers did not significantly enhanced the results. Also, addition of layers had direct impact on the computational time for training the initial model. Keeping all the aspects at hindsight, the ANN model consisted of three hidden layers. Table 4.1 represents the final specifications of all the classifiers with respect to the work. All the five features followed the final specification as mentioned in Table 4.1 for the entire length of the work for. Fig.4.3 shows the pruned structure of the first trained tree of RF.

Table 4.1 Optimal parameters used during training of different classifier models

Classifier	Final Specifications
DT	Number of Levels: 446, Splitting Criterion: Gini Impurity Index
ANN	Network Configuration: 3 layers (20-20-1), Normalization: Min-Max, Weight and Biases: Nguyen-Widrow Method, Activation Function: Tan-sig, Training Function: Levenberg-Marquardt Optimization, Error Goal: 0.001, Epochs: 500
Ensemble learning	Boosting: Gentle Boost, Method: Generative Ensemble, Learning Cycles: 300

RF	Splitting Criterion: Gini-Index, Min sample split: 5, Min sample leaf: 2, Max depth: 25, Max features: Auto, Max leaf node: None, Alpha: 0.0, Bootstrap: True, Number of trees: 100, Learning Cycles: 100,
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4.2.3.2. Testing of Training Module

An entirely separate set of testing data have been for testing the performance of the trained modules. Features for the test samples are extracted using the same moving-window feature extraction technique and are then used as input in the already trained classifier modules. Individual result of each classifier on the test data is obtained and analyzed for determining the performance efficacy of all four classifiers. The result section includes a detailed analysis of all four classifiers.

Fig. 4.2 Diagrammatic representation of the proposed method.

Fig. 4.3 The pruned structure of the first trained tree of random forest classifier.

4.3. Results from CHB-MIT

The seizure detection capability of the classifiers has been authenticated for patient dependent approach as well as for generalized processed features. Accuracy, specificity, and sensitivity have been considered as evaluation parameters. In this work, detection capability of different classifiers has been studied using kappa analysis, MCC, and F1 score. Equations (4.7) to (4.13) presents the formulas used to calculate the indicators.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{(\text{TruePos} + \text{TrueNeg})}{(\text{TruePos} + \text{TrueNeg} + \text{FalsePos} + \text{FalseNeg})} \quad (4.7)$$

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{\text{TruePos}}{\text{Pos}} = \frac{\text{TruePos}}{(\text{TruePos} + \text{FalseNeg})} \quad (4.8)$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{\text{TrueNeg}}{\text{Neg}} = \frac{\text{TrueNeg}}{(\text{FP} + \text{TrueNeg})} \quad (4.9)$$

$$\text{False positive rate} = \frac{\text{FalsePos}}{\text{Neg}} = \frac{\text{FalsePos}}{(\text{FalsePos} + \text{TrueNeg})} \quad (4.10)$$

$$\text{Kappa Analysis (k)} = \frac{P_O - P_E}{1 - P_E} = 1 - \frac{1 - P_O}{1 - P_E} \quad (4.11)$$

where, P_E represents hypothetical probability of chance agreement while P_O stands for relative observed agreement.

$$F_1 \text{ Score} = \frac{2\text{TruePos}}{2\text{TruePos} + \text{FalsePos} + \text{FalseNeg}} \quad (4.12)$$

$$MCC = \frac{\text{TruePos} \times \text{TrueNeg} - \text{FalsePos} \times \text{FalseNeg}}{\sqrt{(\text{TruePos} + \text{FalsePos})(\text{TruePos} + \text{FN})(\text{TrueNeg} + \text{FalsePos})(\text{TrueNeg} + \text{FalseNeg})}} \quad (4.13)$$

where, TruePos is correct classification of positive sample, FalsePos stands for false classification of negative samples as positive, TrueNeg denotes correct classification of negative samples and FalseNeg is for false classification positive samples as negative.

4.3.1. Patient-Specific Performance on Raw Signal

Firstly, a patient dependent approach has been followed with raw electroencephalogram signals to analyze the performance of learning-based methods. Each patient has been used for assessing the detection capacity of the classification framework. Table 4.2 presents the detailed compilation of all the results obtained from different classifiers for each patient. As seen from the Table, with a single exception the accuracy ranged between 75% and 99%. The exception was consistent across all classifiers. Both specificity and sensitivity followed the same trend as accuracy and recorded in the range of 70% to 100% and 75% to 95% respectively. There was exception when it came to attending high accuracy as one specific patient file always documented a high accuracy irrespective of classifiers. Fig.4.4 presented patient-specific seizure detection accuracy for each classifier.

Table 4.2 Performance of different classifiers with raw signals

Methods Used	Patient	Accuracy (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	F ₁ Score	Matthew's Correlation Coefficient	Kappa
DT	P1	83.4	90.4	78.5	0.847	0.679	0.745
	P2	88.4	89.0	87.8	0.885	0.767	0.768
	P3	89.7	87.5	92.3	0.894	0.796	0.796
	P4	84.2	92.3	78.6	0.856	0.696	0.681
	P5	61.9	61.9	61.9	0.619	0.239	0.238
	P6	98.5	99.4	97.6	0.985	0.970	0.970
	P7	79.9	77.8	82.4	0.792	0.600	0.600
	P8	74.1	82.6	69.1	0.771	0.500	0.482
	P9	80.6	93.4	73.6	0.831	0.641	0.612
	P10	76.6	82.7	72.4	0.786	0.539	0.533
	Overall	81.7	85.7	79.4	0.827	0.643	0.643

Ensemble Learning	P1	88.6	86.6	90.8	0.889	0.773	0.772
	P2	91.9	93.1	90.8	0.918	0.839	0.838
	P3	92.5	94.6	90.6	0.923	0.851	0.850
	P4	91.5	88.9	94.4	0.917	0.831	0.830
	P5	62.8	64.5	61.4	0.605	0.258	0.256
	P6	99.6	99.2	100.0	0.996	0.992	0.992
	P7	82.1	86.6	78.6	0.810	0.648	0.642
	P8	78.0	75.1	81.6	0.792	0.564	0.560
	P9	85.0	78.1	96.4	0.866	0.722	0.700
	P10	83.6	81.2	86.4	0.842	0.674	0.672
	Overall	85.6	84.8	87.1	0.856	0.715	0.711
ANN	P1	82.3	76.0	92.7	0.842	0.666	0.647
	P2	93.4	93.8	93.1	0.943	0.869	0.868
	P3	95.1	95.4	94.8	0.951	0.902	0.902
	P4	89.8	85.1	96.0	0.905	0.804	0.796
	P5	63.9	63.1	64.7	0.649	0.278	0.278
	P6	99.5	99.4	99.6	0.995	0.990	0.990
	P7	86.0	89.2	83.3	0.854	0.723	0.720
	P8	74.4	67.8	89.2	0.785	0.528	0.488
	P9	84.3	77.0	97.0	0.862	0.713	0.686
	P10	81.3	80.1	82.5	0.816	0.626	0.628
	Overall	85.0	82.7	89.3	0.860	0.710	0.700
RF	P1	86.9	81.0	95.4	0.880	0.750	0.740
	P2	94.0	93.1	94.9	0.940	0.879	0.880
	P3	96.2	94.1	98.4	0.963	0.925	0.924
	P4	89.3	83.7	97.1	0.901	0.797	0.786
	P5	67.5	66.5	68.7	0.685	0.352	0.350
	P6	99.7	99.4	100.0	0.997	0.994	0.990
	P7	86.1	89.8	83.1	0.855	0.726	0.722
	P8	78.8	72.9	88.9	0.812	0.596	0.576
	P9	82.5	74.4	98.7	0.850	0.689	0.650
	P10	89.0	85.9	92.7	0.895	0.783	0.780

	Overall	87.0	84.1	91.8	0.878	0.749	0.740
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Fig. 4.4 Patient-specific accuracy plot of different classifiers for raw signals.

4.3.2. Generalized Performance of Feature Extracted Signal

Features have been extracted from raw electroencephalogram signals of the complete dataset using a moving window before being fed into the classifier. Table 4.3 accounts for the performance of each classifier for individual feature. For three out of the four classifiers, standard deviation obtained the highest accuracy, with the exception for ensemble learning. Out of the four supervised classifiers, the highest accuracy was achieved by RF at 91.9% for the feature STD. With a 1sec moving window, STD outdid all other feature extraction techniques. Even the misclassified data documented was lowest for random forest. According to the FDR, random forest gave the lowest rate of 0.06/h while ensemble learning and DT stood at 0.1/h., with neural network at 0.07/h. The AUC has been used to facilitate a threshold-free evaluation of the classifiers. Fig.4.5 presents the ROC curve of all classification frameworks for the feature STD. It can be seen from Table 4.4, out of all the features used, energy has acquired the AUC of less than 0.8 for all the classifiers except random forest. The AUC score reached 0.9 across all the classifiers when standard deviation and mean have been used, while for DWT and DFT, it varied slightly. Apart from the F1 score and MCC, kappa value has also been calculated for studying the classifiers. With few exceptions, the classifiers presented almost perfect agreement. ANN and ensemble learning exhibited substantial agreement. The performance accuracy deteriorated irrespective of the classifier when energy has been chosen and therefore, the reliability measure showed moderate agreement. DT displayed substantial agreement while the RF has a nearly seamless agreement except for energy and DWT. The F1 score or also known as the F1 measure

is plotted against the recall value for all the classifiers as shown in Fig.4.6. The CF (confusion matrix) for STD is given in Table 4.5 for both training and testing phases for all the classification frameworks.

Table 4.3 Generalized performance of different classifiers for various features

Type of Classifier	Features	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Accuracy (%)
Decision Tree	STD	91.7	79.7	85.7
	Mean	91.5	79.3	85.4
	DFT	91.9	79.5	85.7
	DWT	79.5	72.9	76.2
	Energy	73.4	69.7	71.6
Ensemble (Gentle-Boost)	STD	91.2	80.1	85.7
	Mean	92.0	81.3	86.6
	DFT	91.7	79.5	85.6
	DWT	87.5	80.4	84.0
	Energy	78.7	77.3	78.0
Artificial Neural Network	STD	94.0	84.0	89.0
	Mean	92.7	84.4	88.6
	DFT	93.2	81.5	87.4
	DWT	87.3	82.1	84.7
	Energy	81.3	70.6	76.0
Random Forest	STD	94.1	89.7	91.9
	Mean	93.9	89.1	91.5
	DFT	94.1	89.0	91.5
	DWT	91.8	80.0	85.9
	Energy	84.7	75.4	80.1

Table 4.4 Statistical measures of different classifiers for various features

Type of Classifier	Features	AUC	F ₁ -Score	Kappa	MCC
Decision Tree	STD	0.917	0.865	0.711	0.719
	Mean	0.914	0.862	0.708	0.713
	DFT	0.919	0.868	0.714	0.720

	DWT	0.795	0.770	0.524	0.525
	Energy	0.734	0.721	0.432	0.431
Ensemble (Gentle-Boost)	STD	0.912	0.864	0.714	0.718
	Mean	0.913	0.873	0.732	0.737
	DFT	0.917	0.864	0.712	0.717
	DWT	0.875	0.845	0.680	0.681
	Energy	0.787	0.781	0.560	0.511
Artificial Neural Network	STD	0.923	0.895	0.780	0.784
	Mean	0.928	0.890	0.838	0.801
	DFT	0.920	0.880	0.748	0.752
	DWT	0.903	0.851	0.700	0.700
	Energy	0.796	0.772	0.520	0.522
Random Forest	STD	0.941	0.921	0.838	0.838
	Mean	0.939	0.917	0.830	0.831
	DFT	0.941	0.917	0.830	0.832
	DWT	0.918	0.867	0.720	0.724
	Energy	0.847	0.790	0.602	0.604

Fig. 4.5 Receiver operating characteristic curve of DT, Ensemble learning, ANN and RF for feature – STD.

Fig. 4.6 F1 Measure vs Recall of four classifiers for different features.

Table 4.5 Confusion matrices of different classifiers for standard deviation

Methods Used	Confusion Matrix				
Decision Tree	Training			Target Class	
				0	1
	CF	Output	0	589246	88
		Class	1	71	589156
	Testing			Target Class	
				0	1
CF	Output	0	201380	20971	
	Class	1	51182	231561	
Artificial Neural Network	Training			Target Class	
				0	1
	CF	Output	0	587244	8598
		Class	1	2073	580246
	Testing			Target Class	
				0	1
CF	Output	0	212129	15138	
	Class	1	40433	237398	
	Training			Target Class	
				0	1
	CF	Output	0	534781	66079
		Class	1	54536	523165

Ensemble Learning	Testing CF			Target Class	
				0	1
		Output	0	202287	22151
		Class	1	50275	230381
Random Forest	Training CF			Target Class	
				0	1
		Output	0	589317	0
		Class	1	0	589244
	Testing CF			Target Class	
				0	1
		Output	0	226514	14974
		Class	1	26048	237558

4.3.3. Performance of Data Splitting

Validation of the suggested approach has been done by separating the data with respect to patients. The split for the two phases is done according to patient files i.e., training has 70% patients while testing has 30% patients. Few cases of the split have been presented in Fig.4.7. Recordings from several patients aided in developing the two subsets as shown in Fig. 4.7. Different combinations have been tested, but only 3 cases have been shown in Fig.4.7. As STD has time and again proved to work better, the performance measure given in Table 4.6 for the mentioned three cases has been for STD. For arbitrarily selected test cases (Table 4.6) random forest reached the highest accuracy and the accuracy lying in the permissible range of $\pm 2\%$. The prescribed framework has been capable of discerning between normal and seizure phases but the uniformity among the presented instances showed mixed outcome. Although the test cases have shown results within an error margin of $\pm 2\%$ yet there remained cases recording mixed results. Thus, to address this constraint multiple case instances are needed where data is partitioned with random selection. This would be followed by training and testing along with subsequent fine tuning of parameters to make the model robust. Hence, robust classifier is needed with more finesse in seizure detection.

Table 4.6 Performance of classifiers for different test scenarios using STD as feature

Test Case	Method	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Accuracy (%)
Case 1	RF	92.5	92.2	92.0

	DT	95.0	79.7	85.5
	ENS	89.6	82.0	85.2
	ANN	95.1	81.5	86.9
Case 2	RF	91.9	90.5	91.2
	DT	85.5	83.3	84.3
	ENS	84.9	83.2	84.0
	ANN	86.9	84.5	86.6
Case 3	RF	93.2	89.9	91.5
	DT	84.7	84.5	84.6
	ENS	84.7	84.2	84.6
	ANN	88.7	85.6	87.1

Fig. 4.7 Few instances of splitting the training and testing set with respect to patients.

4.4. Results from SWEC Dataset

The SWEC dataset has been used for validation and results are mentioned in Table 4.7 for all classifiers and features used in the proposed method. The sensitivity recorded between 76% to 96%, while accuracy was lying in the range of 81% to 96.9% and while specificity was from 86% to 99%. The second dataset performed well with RF and ENS out of the four frameworks with RF achieving the highest accuracy. As STD features worked well, so F1-measure plot for STD across the classifiers for both datasets is shown in Fig. 4.8. The seizure detection rate of the random forest framework for the

second dataset has accomplished suggestively upgraded results than the obtained results for CHB-MIT dataset.

Table 4.7 Performance of SWEC dataset for different classifiers

Classifier	Features	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Accuracy (%)	MCC	F1 Score
Decision Tree	STD	94.6	91.2	92.9	0.872	0.929
	Mean	87.4	93.8	90.5	0.824	0.892
	DFT	91.5	92.5	92.0	0.856	0.915
	DWT	77.6	86.5	82.1	0.661	0.822
	Energy	87.2	90.7	89.3	0.859	0.882
Ensemble Learning	STD	91.4	96.3	93.9	0.889	0.917
	Mean	90.0	96.6	93.3	0.878	0.919
	DFT	92.8	96.3	94.7	0.904	0.938
	DWT	82.4	91.9	87.2	0.764	0.873
	Energy	94.6	93.9	94.3	0.890	0.943
Artificial neural network	STD	84.3	96.6	90.5	0.828	0.878
	Mean	88.4	94.3	91.3	0.842	0.894
	DFT	89.5	92.5	91.0	0.834	0.903
	DWT	76.6	86.6	81.6	0.649	0.821
	Energy	90.4	92.6	91.5	0.841	0.912
Random Forest	STD	96.6	98.6	96.9	0.945	0.963
	Mean	91.0	99.1	95.1	0.913	0.936
	DFT	95.7	98.1	96.1	0.929	0.954
	DWT	85.2	92.4	88.8	0.791	0.893
	Energy	96.6	94.9	96.1	0.918	0.958

Fig. 4.8 F1-Measure of all classifiers for the feature STD for CHB-MIT data set and SWEC dataset.

4.5. Discussion

The main intention of the work has been to design an improved channel independent and patient independent epileptic seizure detection method that provides better accuracy. It can be observed from the results of the proposed method that the detection accuracy is promising. To find a suitable method, the seizure discerning competence of different methods has been studied comprehensively. Generally, frequency domain-based methods lack information belonging to time-domain. Due to this, the time-frequency-based feature extraction technique has been used such that features related to both domains are obtained during the extraction phase. As the present work applied a generalized framework, therefore, seizures affecting any location or type can be perceived with outmost sensitivity. Also, the proposed method analyzed the inclusive seizure detection capability of each classifier. As an alternative to using the orthodox approach of CV, and also to acknowledge the shortcomings and pitfalls, the test sample method has been analyzed that has close semblance to realistic situation. Hence, the work focused on the accompanying complexities of a seizure detection system apart from the usual evaluation of different classifiers, such that cost and energy-efficient hardware implementation can be designed in future.

4.6. Conclusion

The key intention behind the work lies in recommending an effective approach that ensures channel and patient independence, and has an improved detection accuracy of seizures instances.

- A moving window of 1sec has been used for feature extraction from electroencephalogram signals and these features belonged to different domains.
- Despite being the most computationally intensive training model, random forest had the best performance in identifying seizures. As a result, there is room to improve the performance of the said classifier. The selection of relevant classifier and feature for accurate detection algorithm still poses difficulty.
- Designing cost as well as energy efficient tree-based hardware model would be the future direction of the proposed work as tree-based models are lightweight, transferrable, and appropriate to be implemented on a chip.

Chapter 5: A Generalized Deep Learning based Method for Detection of Pediatric Epileptic Seizures

In this chapter study, a long short-term memory-based novel deep learning algorithm has been designed that is efficient in seizure detection from raw electroencephalogram recordings. The proposed solution is based on a straightforward design that incorporates all phases into a single system. Careful thought has been given to avoid loss of generality when there is variation in the electroencephalogram recordings while implementing the LSTM network. Scalp EEG recordings are known to be prone to artifacts. Despite this, the proposed strategy lowered the FDR and augmented the system's overall epilepsy episode discovery accuracy. Also, the proposed deep learning method (LSTM) has been instrumental in studying the integral temporal characteristics of EEG recordings. As one-dimensional raw EEG data has been used hence, it did not involve transformation operation and helped in considerably reducing the model's computational complexity. Furthermore, handcrafted features are not required by the proposed method, therefore a substantial amount of preprocessing of the signal is circumvented. To make the work even more impactful a subsequent database (SWEC) has been used for comprehending the efficacy of the proposed approach, thus raising the chance of a generalized real-time implementation.

5.1. Techniques Used

5.1.1. Convolutional Neural Network

In the last few years, deep learning method that has garnered reputation in the domain of machine learning is CNN or convolutional neural network [140]. CNN has been predominantly used in image processing applications, but with modifications it has also been adapted for identification of medical signals. To process biomedical signals like EEG recordings, 1D-CNN are seemingly suitable. The central architecture of CNN is changed accordingly to make it capable of processing 1D EEG signals. As there are fewer variables involved with 1D architecture, it makes it simpler and faster than 2D CNN architecture [84]. Convolution layers inherently learn various spectral, temporal, and spatial properties from raw EEG signals. The pooling layer that precedes reduces the dimension of features while also avoiding unnecessary repetition. It also assists in avoiding the issue of data overfitting that often plagues deep networks. The most commonly used pooling method out of different pooling methods is max-pooling. Apart

from convolutional and pooling layers, another key component of CNN is the FC (fully connected) layer [141]. Fully connected layer provides the logic and reasoning required for classification of each class. The architecture of the 1D-CNN used in the proposed work is shown in Fig.5.1. Convolutional operation for 1D CNN is represented as:

$$X_j^L = f_{ac}(\sum_{i=1}^C X_i^{L-1} \cdot Ke_{ij}^L + Bi_j^L) \quad (5.1)$$

where, convolutional layer is L, activation function is denoted by f_{ac} , Bi signifies the bias, Ke denotes convolutional kernels while C denotes channels used for input.

Batch normalization is given by the following equation:

$$BN(x_{Ke}) = \alpha_{MB} \left(\frac{x_{Ke} - \mu_{MB}}{\sqrt{\sigma_{MB^2} + \varepsilon}} \right) \quad (5.2)$$

where, α_{MB} denotes variance (mini-batch) is, μ_{MB} is mean (mini-batch), scalar parameter σ_{MB^2} and noise denoted by ε .

Adam optimizer uses Eq 5.3 and 5.4 for calculating first and second moment:

$$mo_t = \beta_1 mo_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_1) gr_t \quad (5.3)$$

$$va_t = \beta_2 va_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_2) gr_t^2 \quad (5.4)$$

where, first moment (mean) is mo_t , and second moment (uncentered variance) is va_t , the decay rates are designated by β_1 and β_2 and gradient represented by gr . When first and second moment gets bias corrected, it is written as:

$$\widehat{mo}_t = \frac{mo_t}{1 - \beta_1^t} \quad (5.5)$$

$$\widehat{va}_t = \frac{va_t}{1 - \beta_2^t} \quad (5.6)$$

Adam optimization is represented as:

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t - \frac{\eta}{\sqrt{\widehat{va}_t + \varepsilon}} \widehat{mo}_t \quad (5.7)$$

where, η is the general learning rate.

The loss function used is binary cross-entropy and is obtained using Eq 5.8:

$$Loss = - \frac{1}{output_size} \sum_{i=0}^{output_size} y_i \cdot \log(\widehat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \cdot \log(1 - \widehat{y}_i) \quad (5.8)$$

Fig. 5.1. The proposed 1D-CNN architecture.

5.1.2. Long Short-Term Memory Network

Improvement in the RNN is reflected in the long short-term memory (LSTM) [84] that addresses the shortcomings of RNN in form of vanishing gradient problems. The LSTM is a sort of RNN that has more associations per cell and can process and retain data for a longer period of time. The repeating module in an LSTM model has a chain-like design with distinct framework [98]. The mode of communication between the interrelating layers of an LSTM network has its exclusive technique that differs from that of an RNN model. The basic building block in an LSTM network is the memory block also known as cell [142]. Different gates are responsible for different operations and the unhindered forward flow of data is maintained by the cell state [143]. The LSTM network is represented in Fig.5.2., while the single LSTM cell structure is depicted in Fig.5.3. Different gates with their individual weights are equivalent to series

of matrix operations and these gates play a crucial role in memorizing the process. The cell candidate (n), forget gate (Fg), input gate (x), and output gate (Op) are the most common gates present in an LSTM architecture [144]. The subsequent equations (5.9 – 5.17) represent the working of different gates.

$$Fg_t = \sigma(W_{Fg}[Hi_{t-1}, I_t] + B_{Fg}) \quad (5.9)$$

$$x_t = \sigma(W_x[Hi_{t-1}, I_t] + B_x) \quad (5.10)$$

$$n_t = \tanh(W_n[Hi_{t-1}, I_t] + B_n) \quad (5.11)$$

$$Ce_t = Ce_{t-1}Fg_t + n_t x_t \quad (5.12)$$

$$Ce_t = Ce_{t-1}\sigma(W_{Fg}[Hi_{t-1}, I_t] + B_{Fg}) + \tanh(W_n[Hi_{t-1}, I_t] + B_n)\sigma(W_x[Hi_{t-1}, I_t] + B_x) \quad (5.13)$$

$$Op_t = \sigma(W_{Op}[Hi_{t-1}, I_t] + B_{Op}) \quad (5.14)$$

$$Hi_t = Op_t \tanh(Ce_t) \quad (5.15)$$

$$Hi_t = \sigma(W_{Op}[Hi_{t-1}, I_t] + B_{Op})\tanh(Ce_{t-1}Fg_t + n_t x_t) \quad (5.16)$$

$$Hi_t = \sigma(W_{Op}[Hi_{t-1}, I_t] + B_{Op})\tanh\left(Ce_{t-1}\sigma(W_{Fg}[Hi_{t-1}, I_t] + B_{Fg}) + \tanh(W_n[Hi_{t-1}, I_t] + B_n)\sigma(W_x[Hi_{t-1}, I_t] + B_x)\right) \quad (5.17)$$

Fig. 5.2. The LSTM structure for seizure detection.

Fig.5.3. A LSTM cell with different gates.

5.2. Proposed Methodology

5.2.1. Architectural Details of the Proposed Method

The graphic representation of seizure detection architecture is presented in Fig.5.4. Raw electroencephalogram recordings have been used for the identification of seizures. The main goal of the work is to design a seizure detection framework that is channel independent, hence as input all the recorded EEG channels (23) have been used as input. The data sample is arbitrarily partitioned into training and testing subgroups with the trained module into further subsequent partitioning to perform concurrent validation. The collection module comprised of base network structures, and the network structure, learnable parameters of the optimizer, layers, and loss function were all set for training during the initialization phase. Comparison of different classifiers are based on the training time and hyper-parameter choices. The cross-validated trained models are saved to be used in the future. The trained models are then evaluated using a different test dataset.

Fig.5.4. The graphic presentation of the proposed seizure detection method.

Fig.5.5 presents the structure of the ANN. The architecture of the 1D-CNN as shown in Fig.5.1 consist of two 1DConv layers for learning the features from raw EEG signals. This is followed by batch normalization with the final layer as the max-pooling layer. The second convolutional block has the same structure. The flatten layer is responsible for converting the feature maps into 1D vector which are then connected to the dense layer for the classification. The activation function in the first three dense layers is tanh with a subsequent dropout layer. The output vector according to the two classes is generated by the final dense layer that has sigmoid as the activation function. As seen from the LSTM network in Fig.5.2, the memory units present in the LSTM block are 256 with ReLU activation function and different gates form these memory units while unwanted information is removed by the forget gate. The input gate is accountable for the addition of information and the regulatory filter uses sigmoid function that is multiplied before getting summed to the cell state. The output gate finally extracts the useful information. The sequence length does not have direct impact on the training of the model. Varying the sequence length is synonymous to adding more training examples for the model. In the present work, the sequence length has been changed but since it did not impact the performance significantly hence the length has been set at 5.

In various previous works, variants of LSTM models have been used by authors. Some have used nested LSTM model while in other convolutional LSTM, deep-CLSTM and bi-directional LSTM network have been used for studying seizure. When compared to other LSTM models used previously, the number of units in the LSTM layer is large and that has helped in efficiently distinguishing between normal and seizure activity from raw EEG signal. Thus, the proposed model has shown the capability of discerning epileptic signals without the need of an additional step of feature extraction while in other LSTM models, either feature is extracted or an additional convolutional layer is added to extract features before being fed to the LSTM network. As training a LSTM network is essentially time consuming, and EEG signals results in large dataset, hence a simple network has been selected that would bring down the training time comparatively. Also, when the sequence length of the signal is changed, the number of parameters generated remains the same, the network size is not affected which is another promising advantage of LSTM network. Although a simple LSTM framework has been used for the proposed method, the network structure is different. The number of units of the LSTM layer has been altered and modifications have been made and tested before finalizing the proposed network structure.

LSTM networks are said to be suitable for time series signals and as EEG recordings belong to the same category, utilizing the capabilities of LSTM network has been done for seizure detection. The subtle changes present in the EEG recordings over a time frame can be analyzed using the facility of sequence present in the LSTM network. The LSTM network in the proposed method received input from multiple EEG channels and the EEG recordings have been assigned to the network in sequence of preictal and ictal recording. The sequence of the LSTM network is altered and tested before settling the final sequence number. As generalized approach has been used by the LSTM network, large number of EEG segments comprising of both preictal and ictal phases have been included and this helped in distinguishing between the variations in EEG signals. To avoid over-fitting, the EEG segments for each patient are randomly selected and shuffled before being fitted as input into the LSTM network. EEG signals are complex and the relationship among the different domains (spatial, temporal and spectral) is strong. Therefore, when input data is fed into the model, keeping the relations intact is crucial. In this work, as all the EEG channels have been considered therefore, column kernel has been used in the LSTM unit such that all the channels are covered with minimum distortion. The competency of retaining information over a time

period helped in understanding and analyzing the EEG signal. Looping through the time sequence helped in better training of the EEG signal which in turn helped in better seizure detection with maximum accuracy and minimum error. Table 5.1 presents the detailed information of all the classifiers. Correspondingly, the learning parameters of all classifiers are mentioned in Table 5.2.

Table 5.1. Brief summary of the classifiers

Classifier Used	Block	Layer	Neurons Present	Additional Parameters
Artificial Neural Network (ANN)	Input	Dense	128	Activation: ReLU
	Hidden	Dense	256	Activation: ReLU
	Output	Dense	1	Activation: Sigmoid
1D Convolutional Neural Network (1D-CNN)	Conv1	Convolution	128	Kernel size: 3
		Activation	128	Activation: ReLU
		Batch Normalization	128	-
		Max Pooling	128	Pool size: 2
	Conv1	Convolution	128	Kernel size: 3
		Activation	128	Activation: ReLU
		Batch Normalization	128	-
Fully connected	Fully connected 1	Dense	64	-
		Drop-out	64	Activation: tanh 0.2
	Fully connected 2	Dense	32	-
		Drop-out	32	Activation: tanh 0.2
Fully connected 3	Dense	64	-	
	Drop-out	64	Activation: tanh 0.2	
Fully connected 4	Dense	1	Activation: Sigmoid	

				Regularization: L ₂
Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)	LSTM	LSTM	256	Activation: ReLU
	Fully connected	Dense	128	Activation: ReLU
	Fully connected	Dense	1	Activation: Sigmoid Regularization: L ₂

Fig. 5.5. The structure of the proposed ANN.

Table 5.2. Learning parameters of different classifiers

Classifier Used	Additional Parameters
Artificial Neural Network (ANN)	Optimizer: Adam
	Loss_Function: Binary Cross Entropy
	beta1: 0.9, beta2: 0.999
	Learning_rate: 0.0001
	Epochs: 100
	Batch_Size: 200
1D Convolutional Neural Network (1D-CNN)	Optimizer: Adam
	Loss_Function: Binary Cross Entropy
	beta1: 0.9, beta2: 0.999

	Learning_rate: 0.001
	Epochs: 200
	Batch_Size: 600
Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)	Optimizer: Adam
	Loss_Function: Binary Cross Entropy
	L2 regularization Factor: 0.0001
	Sequence: 5
	Epochs: 1000
	Batch_Size: 600

5.2.2. Training and Testing Approach

A cross-validation approach has been used to measure the dependability of the proposed deep learning approach. The EEG recordings have been segregated into N folds that contained identical duration of both seizure and non-seizure phases. The test data is made of one-fold from the N folds of data, for evaluation of the trained models. For training and validation of models, the remaining (N – 1) folds have been used. In each of the fold, 20% of the training data validated the respective model simultaneously while residual 80% of the data trained the model. The error rate is calculated at the completion of each epoch, such that overfitting can be avoided. Usually, a continuous rise in error rate for four successive epochs leads to the termination of the training process. When the training process attains completion, evaluation is carried using the test fold and the process gets repeated unless all folds are exhausted. The detection capability of the classifiers has been studied using cross-validation.

5.3. Results

The proposed approach has been corroborated and tested using classical as well as deep learning methods on raw EEG recordings from the two datasets. Metrics such as precision, sensitivity, accuracy, specificity, FPR, MCC, and F1-measure have been used to evaluate efficiency of different classifiers. To comprehend the precision of the method, convergence analysis has also been performed.

5.3.1. Performance of Different Classifiers on CHB-MIT Dataset

In the designing of an automatic seizure detection module, the present study has included ANN, 1D-CNN, and LSTM. Table 5.3 presents the classification results of CHB-MIT dataset. As seen from the Table, deep learning-based classifiers furnished better detection accuracy than the traditional approach when raw electroencephalogram

signals are considered. LSTM provided a FPR of 0.003/h whereas the presence of seizure is detected by 1D-CNN at a rate of 0.034/h and by ANN with a FPR rate of 0.044/h. The LSTM network registered the highest precision among the three classifiers. The accuracy curves of two out of the three methods for training epochs are displayed in Fig.5.6. Both accuracy and loss curve are illustrated for LSTM in Fig.5.7 thus making it a slightly different plot.

Table 5.3. Performance metric of different learning models using 10-fold CV on non-invasive CHB-MIT dataset

Classifier	Artificial Neural Network	1D Convolutional Neural Network	Long Short-Term Memory Network
Sensitivity (%)	92.3	94.7	99.9
Precision (%)	95.6	96.9	99.9
Specificity (%)	95.8	97.1	99.9
Accuracy (%)	94.3	96.5	99.9
False Positive Rate (per h.)	0.044	0.034	0.003
MCC	0.872	0.899	0.999
F ₁ Score	0.940	0.958	0.999

Fig. 5.6. The accuracy plot of (a) ANN, (b) 1D CNN for CHB-MIT dataset.

Fig. 5.7. Accuracy-loss plot of LSTM network for CHB-MIT dataset.

5.3.2. Performance of Different Classifiers on SWEC Dataset

A second dataset containing intracranial EEG (iEEG) from the Sleep-Wake-Epilepsy-Center (SWEC) has been utilized to test the competence of the suggested technique. During validation, the parametric configuration of all the trained modules remained unaltered. The evaluation of different models on the second dataset is shown in Table 5.4. The performance metrics resembled that of the CHB-MIT dataset. The proposed model was capable of meeting the requirement of lowering the false detection and boosting the sensitivity, which is the standard of an efficient detection system. The false-positive rate is analogous to the previous dataset with 0.006/h for LSTM, 0.002/h for 1D-CNN and 0.075/h for ANN. Fig. 5.9 illustrates the bar-graph representation of F1 measure or F1 score and FPR per hour (/h) for both datasets. The curves of accuracy and loss of the SWEC dataset for the LSTM framework is shown in Fig.5.8.

Table 5.4. Performance metric of validation on SWEC dataset for different classifiers

Classifier	Artificial Neural Network	1D Convolutional Neural Network	Long Short-Term Memory Network
Sensitivity (%)	94.4	97.3	99.4
Precision (%)	95.4	100.0	99.2
Specificity (%)	95.6	100.0	99.3
Accuracy (%)	94.7	98.1	99.5
False Positive Rate (per h)	0.075	0.002	0.006
MCC	0.880	0.974	0.987

F ₁ Score	0.938	0.986	0.993
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Fig.5.8. Accuracy-loss of LSTM network for SWEC dataset.

(a)

(b)

Fig.5.9. Performance analysis between CHB-MIT and SWEC with respect to (a) F1 Measure and (b) False Positive Rate (Per Hour).

5.3.3. Convergence Analysis of the Proposed Seizure Detection Method

When an algorithm generates lowest error in succession over a long time, it is said to have converged. As they execute gradient-based optimization, deep learning methods assist algorithms to converge to the global minima. The convergence analysis is used to determine the algorithm's approximate balance and accuracy and for the suggested work the loss value has been used to examine the algorithm's convergence. It can be seen from Fig.5.10 that for over multiple epochs the objective function remains the same. For LSTM network the loss function progressively decreases and stabilizes after a specific number of iterations. Even for the second dataset, as shown in Fig.5.8, the loss function converges and persists throughout the time.

Fig.5.10. Loss convergence curve of (a) 1D-CNN and (b) Long Short-Term Memory for CHB-MIT dataset.

5.4. Discussion

For both scalp and intracranial EEG recordings, the recommended approach is discussed as a seizure detection system. Specific selection of EEG channel is not opted, as all channels have been considered as input thus making it a channel-independent approach. Comparison has been made with other related methods for evaluating the detection capability of the system. Usage of both, scalp as well as intracranial electroencephalogram signal in the same epilepsy detection module is less in number. The projected work has exploited this idea with an aim to design a robust and inclusive system that has the capability of seamlessly adapting to different types of EEG recordings and detecting the presence of seizures efficiently.

The ability to achieve high classification accuracy depends on various factors that play important parts like, data processing techniques, model design, and parameter selection. But there are times when trivial changes in the constraint can restrict the performance of the system. Therefore, an epileptic seizure detection unit requires models that have independent learning capability and changes in parameters do not inflict change in performance. Since the proposed LSTM network circumvents the laborious step of feature mining, when the module has been trained and saved, it can be utilized to recognize EEG recordings in future. The goal of the current research is to improve the quality of life of people with intractable epilepsy. Because the study did not focus on seizure detection latency, it can be included in future studies. This would add immense assistance in the development of an operational alarm producing system capable of triggering an alarm anytime it detects abnormalities in EEG signals prior to seizure onset. High classification accuracy requires large storage, and memory bandwidth, thus

making their deployment challenging, especially for energy-constrained platforms such as portable devices. In general, the implementation complexity and performance of deep neural networks depend on the tasks to be completed. Larger models lead to more computations, thus overwhelming general CPU. As alternative the approach of parallel computing has been considered. However, in addition to the high-power consumption of GPU, the inherent recurrent characteristics of LSTM poses as a bottleneck for parallel processing on GPU. Due to this reason, the approach that has garnered attention in LSTM implementation is FPGA because of its low energy consumption, low latency, high performance and reconfigurability. Apart from this widely used open-source deep learning frameworks are available that allows rapid deployment of deep learning models for training. Above all the acceptability of the model will depend on the three categories of, accuracy index, performance index such as latency, power consumption etc., and resource index such as utilization of RAM, look up tables etc.

5.5. Conclusion

In the present work there is no arbitrary selection of channels and all recorded channels have been used as input such that seizures relating to any location and hemisphere can be perceived with ease. As huge volumes of data are generated from complex EEG recordings, hence deep learning models have made their presence known in the field of research by displaying their competence and efficacy. LSTM network has been employed in the suggested method to investigate and detect seizures. When the metrics are compared, low FPR and high sensitivity have been recorded by the proposed model which are mostly considered as standards for any seizure detection system. As the results are promising, therefore, further extensive testing is essential before it can be implemented in a clinical set-up.

Chapter 6: Discussions

The thesis addresses the analysis of non-invasive and invasive electroencephalogram (EEG) signals for the detection of epileptic seizures. The effectiveness of a machine learning-based algorithm is described and with the help of accurate determination of seizure has been performed from the scalp as well as intracranial data. The results obtained from different analyses have been compared with previous studies to further scrutinize and project a comparison. The proposed methods show favorable performance when determined by well-defined performance metrics. Also, patient-specific as well as generalized approaches have been followed and it is seen that the generalized method has fared fine when cross-validation has been performed. Hence, it can be safely inferred that when all patients and channels have been considered, the seizure detection capability of the proposed approaches has shown commendable results.

6.1. Contributions and Main Findings

The thesis contributes to the field of research associated with machine learning and deep learning algorithms to detect epileptic seizures from EEG signals in a channel independent and patient independent setting. More precisely, the three works compare different traditional classifiers (ANN, DT, RF, ENS) along with deep learning algorithms (1D CNN and LSTM) for generalized seizure detection. Furthermore, the proposed generalized approaches have been validated with a second intracranial dataset that has shown promising results for the patient-specific approach.

6.2. In Relation to Previous Works

Results obtained from proposed approaches have been compared to existing methods with respect to features and classifiers for the CHB-MIT dataset. As seen in Chen et al. [23], their proposed work was based on different wavelet decomposition and achieved an accuracy of 87% on the CHB-MIT dataset. Thus, the proposed work based on wavelet decomposition has improved the seizure detection accuracy by nearly 9% using Symlet that worked effectively in extracting features from signals belonging to different parts of the brain. Frequency domain-based methods such as invariant scattering [49] transform and Fourier transform [44] have been used in patient-specific approaches but there is an absence of time-related features of electroencephalogram signals. In [40] authors have used STFT for better time resolution with poor frequency resolution. The present work considered both time and frequency related features, giving better

accuracy in detecting almost all seizure instances present in the recordings for both generalized as well as patient dependent approaches. One of the gold-standard works in seizure detection for the CHB-MIT dataset is that of Shoeb [145]. The author used wavelet decomposition and support vector machine for detection of seizure onset in a patient dependent approach. As seen from the comparison table (Table 6.1), the proposed work obtained higher sensitivity than [145] and the misclassification rate is also lower for the generalized approach. Deep learning-based networks are sort after as they are considered superior because of their innate ability of extracting features without the necessity for the additional practice. But these convoluted layers are complex, hence making the deep learning structures complicated. Therefore, when complexity is taken into account, the present work is less intricate and hence has a fair chance of being considered for system-on-chip implementation. The correlation coefficient has been used for studying the characteristic of different channels by Diwaker et al. [146]. This approach is effective pertaining to a particular dataset and would vary among other patients, increasing the misclassification rate. The presented work considered all the 23 channels and has given equal weightage to all the channels. Since, the main aim of the work is to design a generalized training module that would be effective for any patient, arbitrary selection of channels is avoided. Comparison has been studied based on advanced seizure detection models. On-chip feature extraction and classification model have been designed in [147] using 8 channels. It was capable of detecting epileptic seizures with an accuracy of 95.1%. Although the proposed work did not address the on-chip seizure detection unit, but it has used 23 bipolar electroencephalogram channels for the detection of seizures. A closed-loop system-on-chip has been designed by Chen et al. [148] that is invasive and has been tested on animals, while the prototype of the proposed method is non-invasive which will be suitable for pediatric patients. Mirzaei et al. [149] suggested an asynchronous seizure detection block for implantable devices with the capability of ending the development of a seizure attack. Both the approaches are built around the concept of invasive approach or using intracranial EEG recordings. But, invasive approaches, in the long run, encounters the problem of scar tissue-related complications. Scalable SOC (system-on-chip) comprising of a feature extraction unit and a classification unit has been proposed by Yoo et al. [150]. With 8 EEG channels, the SOC unit achieved a classification accuracy of 84.4% for the CHB-MIT dataset. Although superior epileptic seizure detection units [151] are present, the present work avoids arbitrary channel

selection as it has the facility of using all electrode channels and holds enough possibility of being converted into a fully system-on-chip design in the future.

Table 6.1 Comparison study of detection performance of the proposed approach with existing works

Authors	Feature	Dataset Used	Algorithm	Channel Specific	Patient Specific	Accuracy (%)
Tsiouris et al. [40]	STFT	CHB	-	-	Yes	92.0
Chen et al. [23]	Wavelet Level Selection	CHB	SVM	-	-	92.3
Thodoroff et al. [152]	-	CHB	Convolutional Neural Network	-	Yes	85.0
Ahmad et al. [44]	Mallat's Scattering	CHB	-	-	Yes	91.0
Bonello and Garg [49]	PSD	CHB	SVM	-	Yes	92.3
Yang et al. [153]	GNMM	BCI Competition Data III	MLP	Yes	-	86.0
Diwaker et al. [146]	CC	BCI Competition Data III	SVM	Yes	-	82.1
Proposed Method	Multi-resolution wavelet transformation	CHB	ANN	No	No	95.3

* '-' means not stated clearly

In [95] authors used 18 EEG channels for discerning seizure for the same data while proposing a channel-independent method, all channels have been considered in the proposed method. The highest sensitivity achieved by the proposed method is 94% in contrast to 82% of the mentioned work for NN. For testing and validation of seizure

detection method, usually patient-specific approach [25, 154] is applied along with k-fold CV method. But a generalized approach has been used for scrutinizing the working of all four classification frameworks. Also, when compared to traditional machine learning methods, the generalized approach has shown improved precision than the patient dependent approach [154] for seizure detection. As seen in [25], approximate energy when used as a feature has provided satisfactory detection accuracy, but when energy is used as the feature, it has reached the lowest accuracy across all classifiers. Except for a few works [95, 25, 63] the proposed approach performed well when compared with prior works. Deep learning method such as convolutional neural network [87] has been compared with the proposed work in the time domain. The analysis shows, the projected approach to obtain better accuracy than the mean accuracy reached while employing deep learning algorithm. The neural network has been extensively used in seizure detection framework [155], where the network configuration has a direct dependency on the processing power of the neural network. Therefore, more intricate the network configuration more is the time complexity. The authors in their previous work [155] used only discrete wavelet transformation and CV for corroboration of the framework which is a prominent variation from the current work.

Table 6.2 Assessment study of the present work with other existing methods on CHB-MIT dataset

Authors	Features	Algorithm	No. of Patient	No. of Samples	Patient Specific	Channel Specific	Accuracy (%)
Kaleem et al. [25]	WT	SVM, LDA	23	1,024 samples per segment	Yes	No	99.6
Siddiqui et al. [63]	Mean. Entropy, etc.	SVM, Ensemble, DT	2	2,520; 1,440 (10s epoch) 50,400; 28,800 (0.5s epoch)	Yes	No	99.5
Boonyakitanton et al. [95]	Bayesian error rate	ANN, CNN	24	1,889 (ANN)	Yes	Yes	98.6

				7,945 (CNN)			
Chakrabarti et al. [155]	DWT	ANN	10	1,688,775 samples	No	No	95.3
Yuan et al. [156]	EEG embedding	WT - CtxEEG	9	4,302 EEG fragments	-	Yes	92.2
Tsiouris et al. [154]	Energy, etc.	NN, SVM	24	121,062 samples each in pre-ictal & inter-ictal phase	Yes	No	86.7
Usman et al. [79]	CNN	SVM	24	32,576 (Training phase)	Yes	No	-
Zhou et al. [87]	-	CNN	24	-	Yes	No	59.5
Proposed Method	1sec window of STD	RF	10	1,178,599 (Training) 505,097 (Testing)	No	No	91.9

Sensitivity is an important parameter in understanding the performance of the system and when compared with Tsiouris et al [86], the LSTM-based suggested approach has the competence of reaching high sensitivity rate following a general method. Generally, Bi-LSTM [79] network holds the benefit of using important data back and forth but when compared in terms of sensitivity, the proposed simple long short-term memory framework fared better. As a generalized approach is an accumulation of EEG recordings from all the patients belonging to the dataset, this helped in perusing the delicate changes present in EEG signals. Hence, the proposed approach has been capable of recognizing most of the epileptic instances than the strategy applied in [91], this made the work more appropriate for real-life application. Also, the FPR of the proposed work is low and has worked exceptionally when compared with other related

works [86, 91, 96, 105, 157, 159], hence cementing the stability of the system and paving way for designing an alarm generation system. Although there is an absence of intricate and deep network structures [92, 97, 100] yet it has managed to attain high accuracy by correctly identifying epileptic seizures.

Fig. 6.1. Comparison of different seizure detection works based on traditional algorithms.

Table 6.3. Comparison of the proposed approach with prior studies on the CHB-MIT dataset

Authors	Methods	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Accuracy (%)	FPR/h	F ₁ Score
Boonyakitont et al. [96]	ScoreNet, Support Vector Machine	76.5	99.2	99.8	0.09	0.701
Hamavar et al. [157]	Change Point Detector	100.0	-	-	0.39	-
Yuan et al. [158]	Short Time Fourier	-	-	93.8	-	0.960

	Transform-SSDA					
Hossain et al. [97]	Deep Convolutional Neural Network	90.0	91.65	98.05	-	-
Wei et al. [100]	Convolutional Neural Network	72.1	95.8	84.0	-	-
Li et al. [105]	Fully Connected - Nested LSTM	95.42	95.29	95.29	0.66	-
Gómez et al. [91]	Convolutional Neural Network	58.3	99.6	99.3	<0.5	0.59
Wen and Zhang [92]	Autoencoder-CDNN	-	-	88.1	-	-
Cao et al. [159]	Short Time Fourier Transform, Convolutional Neural Network	-	-	90.13	0.07	-
Zhou et al. [87]	Convolutional Neural Network	94.2	96.9	95.6	-	-
Usman et al. [79]	Convolutional Neural Network, Support Vector Machine	92.7	90.8	-	-	-

Hu et al. [104]	Bidirectional- LSTM	93.6	91.8	-	-	-
Tsiouris et al. [86]	Long Short-Term Memory	99.8	99.8	-	0.02	
Proposed Work	Long Short-Term Memory	99.9	99.9	99.9	0.003	0.999

Fig. 6.2. Comparison of different seizure detection works based on deep learning algorithms.

6.3. Limitations

When the results of the proposed approaches are assessed, certain limitations related to the studies came to light that requires to be considered. One of the limitations could be the choice of feature extraction and feature selection. How to select features that would be appropriate for discerning epileptic seizures from different EEG recordings in itself is a whole research area. In the present approaches, a naive method of considering all available channels has been chosen and no complex algorithms have been applied for selecting and reducing the feature space. This is to emphasize on the fact that all the approaches applied in the present work are centered around simple architectures and

algorithms to avoid complexity and also there is no inclusion of feature reduction techniques. With further research, the various efficiency measuring parameters can be potentially improved. As this study focused on generalized patient independent classifiers, hence even distribution of electrodes placement has been considered throughout all proposed approaches. Another probable limitation associated is that no attention has been directed towards the presence of artifacts from the EEG recordings. Other than filters that have been used during the original recording of electroencephalogram signals, additional bandpass filters have not been used, therefore the presence of artifacts may impact the results. The key limitation of studies related to machine learning and applied in the medicine domain, sufficient availability of data for training the classifiers. Although two datasets have been used, yet from a machine learning perspective, it is still rather limited as long-duration EEG signals have not been reviewed. Long-duration EEG recordings will tend to have data imbalance in preictal interictal and ictal phases. Hence, proper segmentation will be required before training the classifiers to avoid biased results. Also, there is a possibility that the approaches might fail if or when the signals are not correctly recorded or in situations where one or multiple EEG channels are missing. Yet, despite the limitations, the proposed approaches have managed to present promising results where accuracies ranged over 90% for both the non-invasive (scalp) and invasive (intracranial) datasets that have been tested.

Chapter 7: Conclusion and Future Works

7.1. Conclusion

In this thesis, three different works have been performed for the efficient discerning of epileptic seizures. Firstly, a novel and adaptable method have been proposed based on discrete wavelet decomposition for extraction of feature and artificial neural network for classification of epileptic seizures. An archetype microcontroller-based approach has been presented for enhancing detection accuracy of seizures in a brief amount of time. The proposed circuit has a simple construction, and the microcontroller is adaptable to a variety of sensors. The prototype model's low power consumption acts as an extra benefit, allowing it to be used for seizure detection in real-world situation. The second work suggested a channel-independent method for studying pediatric epilepsy. Features pertaining to different feature areas have been extracted and applied to different classifiers to analyze and find the most fitting framework that would be used suitable for detection of seizure instances. The training time was the least for the decision tree but the downside was the lowest seizure detection accuracy. The highest accuracy was achieved by the RF framework although it being the most exhausting training model. Also, more logic rules are generated by random forest that in turn can enhance the accuracy as compared to the decision tree. In the final work, deep learning methods are used to offer a seizure detection framework irrespective of channel specification. Instead of using specially selected channels, all of the recorded channels are considered to identify seizures originating from any part of the brain. LSTM network has been proposed as a framework for scrutinizing and recognizing epileptic seizures. The proposed deep learning-based approach was able to offer a creditable FPR and F1 score with high sensitivity that are generally considered as acceptable characteristics for an epileptic seizure detection system.

The contribution and impact of the present work can be highlighted as following –

- A generalized deep learning-based model has been designed that is capable of discerning seizure located in any part of the brain.
- The proposed work has been able to reduce the false detection rate considerably which in a way have addressed one out of many shortcomings present in prior works.

- Equal weightage has been given to each channel instead of random channel selection thus leading to a better and robust model which is a difference from previous works.
- Further, a prototype model has been designed that is energy efficient and hence in future can be used for seizure monitoring that would bring an impact in real life situation for patients suffering from epilepsy.

7.2. Future Considerations

To further improve the research work, the number of patients and the amount of data could be increased. From a machine learning perspective, specifically for deep learning algorithms, the amount of data used in each of the works is relatively limited. Therefore, in the future, if classifiers are trained with a large dataset that would possibly benefit in designing a more robust classifier. As EEG signals vary greatly, hence having more patients along with a longer duration of recordings would bring a significant difference in the seizure detection system making it complete and more efficient in dealing with types of epileptic attacks. Variants of different deep learning algorithms could be used that could further reduce the false detection. As EEG signals tend to be unbalanced, segmentation should be considered to reduce the possibility of biases towards one specific class. Additionally, channel selection and feature reduction techniques can be investigated intensively so that redundancy could be avoided. Apart from this, the proposed approaches could be validated in a real-time setup where it would accommodate varying EEG channels for an individual patient and efficiently detect the presence of epileptic seizures. If the frameworks prove to be efficient then possible hardware implementation could be considered that would be portable, cost-effective, lightweight and fit to be implemented on a chip.

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Contributions

Papers

- [1] Chakrabarti, S., Swetapadma, A., & Pattnaik, P. K. (2021). A channel independent generalized seizure detection method for pediatric epileptic seizures. *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, 209, 106335. (Elsevier) (SCI, Impact factor 7.027)
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Conferences and Book Chapter

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Patent

- [1] Chakrabarti, S; Swetapadma, A; & Pattnaik, P. 2022. A generalized epileptic seizure detection framework independent of defined channels. ([Australian Patent No. 2021103639](#)), [IP Australia](#), filed June 26,2021. ([Patent Granted](#))